

1 *Review*

2 **Pangolin Footprints: Infectivity, Virulence and Long** 3 **COVID**

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Abstract: This review focuses on three closely related models that use protein intrinsic disorder to link the N and M to infectivity, virulence and, potentially, long COVID. While the models, Shell Disorder Models (SDMs), were initially created using computational and empirical molecular techniques based on protein intrinsic disorder, experimental and clinical data were continuously used for refinement and checked for reproducibility and reliability of SDMs. Interestingly, SDMs are uniquely able to link the potentially major cause of infectivity, virulence and long COVID under one coherent concept of protein intrinsic disorder. An example of this is SDMs' ability to provide a novel and coherent explanation for the differences in the virulence and infectivity of Omicron, SARS-CoV-1 and non-Omicron SARS-CoV-2. SARS-CoV-2 has been clinically shown to induce much greater shedding of infectious particles in patients. Curiously, all known SARS-CoV-2-related viruses, excluding SARS-CoV-1, have an abnormally hard outer shell (low M disorder), which is associated with burrowing animals, such as rabbits and pangolins. Evidence of a unique molecular and evolutionary relationship ("pangolin footprints") between pangolins and COVID-19 is examined. SDMs suggest that this hard outer shell is responsible for the high infectivity of COVID-19 and, potentially, long COVID, as the hard M provides resistance to the antimicrobial enzymes found in the immune and respiratory systems. The implications could provide clues towards further research involving long COVID and infectivity, including possible reservoirs among macrophages. This also explains clinical observations of the persistence of the virus throughout the body months after infection. In the case of virulence, greater disorder in N contributes to more rapid replication by providing more efficient protein-protein binding. As a results, N disorder correlates with viral titer and therefore virulence and, to some extent, infectivity.

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Keywords: coronavirus; COVID; intrinsic disorder; membrane; nucleocapsid; nucleoprotein; Omicron; pangolin; shell; virulence; long COVID; attenuation; variant; immune; perforin; complement system; macrophage; reservoir; Artificial Intelligence; AI; hard shell; lysosome; unstructured; NL63; spike;

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Abbreviations:

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COVID: Coronavirus Disease; CoV: Coronavirus; SARS: Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome; HCoV: Human coronavirus. SDM: Shell Disorder Model; PONDR[®]-VLXT: Predictor of Natural Disordered Regions using VLXT; PID: Percentage of Intrinsic Disorder (number of disordered residues divided by the total number of residues); Pang2017: SARS-CoV-2 related pangolin-CoV isolated in 2017; Pang2019: Pangolin-CoV isolated in 2019, N: Nucleocapsid protein, M Membrane protein; S: Spike protein; SARS-CoV-2, BANAL: SARS-CoV-2 related Bat-CoVs found in Laos, NL63: A common HCoV; RaTG13: A SARS-CoV-2 related bat-CoV discovered in Yunnan; AI: Artificial intelligence; EBOV: Ebola virus; NiV: Nipah virus; DENV: Dengue virus; HIV: Human immunodeficiency virus; YFV: Yellow fever virus; ZIKV: Zika virus;

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1. Introduction

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1.1 Overview

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This review focuses on the three closely related models as related to COVID-19 (Coronavirus Disease 2019) [1-3]. The models use protein intrinsic disorder to link the N and M to infectivity, virulence and, potentially, long COVID. While the three models, Shell Disorder Models (SDMs) [4], were computationally created using empirical

72 molecular techniques based on protein intrinsic disorder, experimental and clinical data
73 will be examined for the reproducibility and reliability of SDMs. Interestingly, SDMs
74 are uniquely able to link the potentially major cause of infectivity, virulence and long
75 COVID under one coherent concept of protein intrinsic disorder. An example of this is
76 SDMs. For instance, it is able to provide a novel and coherent explanation for the
77 differences in virulence and infectivity between SARS-CoV-1 and SARS-CoV-2, which
78 has been clinically shown to induce much greater shedding of infectious particles in
79 patients. Curiously, all known SARS-CoV-2-related viruses, excluding SARS-CoV-1,
80 have an abnormally hard outer shell (low M disorder), which is associated with
81 burrowing animals, such as rabbits and pangolins. Evidence of a unique molecular and
82 evolutionary relationship (“pangolin footprints”) between pangolins and COVID-19 is
83 examined. SDMs suggests that this hard outer shell is responsible for the high
84 infectivity of COVID-19 and, potentially, long COVID, as the hard M provides
85 resistance to the antimicrobial enzymes found in the immune and respiratory systems.
86 The implications could provide clues towards further research involving long COVID
87 and infectivity, including the search for possible reservoirs among macrophages. This
88 also explains clinical observations of the persistence of the virus throughout the body
89 months after infection. In the case of virulence, greater disorder in N contributes to
90 more rapid replication by providing more efficient protein-protein binding. As a result,
91 N disorder correlates with viral titer and therefore virulence and, to a limited extent,
92 infectivity. As S (spike protein) is currently yet to be part of SDMs, S is mentioned
93 sparingly as part of a discussion involving the potentials and limitations of SDMs. It
94 should also be reminded that while there are current review and research papers that
95 attempt to link various viral proteins to virulence or infectivity [5-8], we will attempt to
96 show that the approach using protein intrinsic disorder provides a more coherent
97 concept that links virulence and infectivity via M and N. S could also be later added to
98 the framework at some point.

99 1.2 Pangolin Footprints: Enigmas of COVID-19 Related Viruses

100 It has been more than 4 years since the first outbreak of COVID-19 [1-3]. Even
101 as we are just beginning to understand what was previously unclear about it,
102 there is still much to be uncovered and resolved. For instance, why is SARS-
103 CoV-2 highly contagious in contrast to 2003 SARS-CoV (SARS-CoV-1, SARS:
104 Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome, CoV: Coronavirus)? The total number of
105 people infected thus far is more than 700 million [3], whereas there were only
106 about 10,000 cases in the 2002-3 SARS outbreak [4]. Why is SARS-Co-2 less
107 virulent and much more infectious than SARS-CoV-1? What are the structural
108 differences responsible for the differences? What is the cause of long COVID?
109 Early in the outbreak it was believed that the reason for the extraordinary
110 contagiousness of COVID-19 lies solely on the Spike (S) protein [9-12]. As more
111 computational, clinical, and experimental data became available, the
112 reproducibility of such a hypothesis can be increasingly questioned even
113 though there are few current papers that examine this issue especially
114 pertaining links between infectivity and virulence in a coherent manner, which
115 we believed is best approached using the concept of protein intrinsic disorder.
116 This paper re-examines the roles of two highly important, though less-
117 researched, proteins: M and N, while keeping the functions of S in mind.

118 The framework of many of the studies were established using an AI tool
119 to study the sequence of the M and N proteins. One important but peculiar
120 discovery using the protein disorder AI tool, PONDR®-VLXT [13-17], is that
121 all SARS-CoV-2-related viruses, not just SARS-CoV-2, have among the hardest
122 outer shells (low M disorder) known within the CoV family [18-21]. It is
123 believed that it is this anomaly pertaining to M that is primarily responsible for
124 the high contagiousness of COVID-19, since a harder M provides greater
125 resistance for the virus against the large array of antimicrobial enzymes present
126 in the saliva and mucus [21-28] and, thus, making it more likely for the host to
127 shed much more infectious particles [29]. N, on the other hand, could help
128 modulate the infectivity and virulence as greater N disorder allows for more
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130 efficient protein-protein/RNA/lipid binding [4,16,30-33] that could lead to
131 more rapid replication of the virus, especially in vital organs [34-40].
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133 A retrospective search after the initial COVID-19 outbreak yielded a bat-
134 CoV sample (RaTG13) obtained from a Yunnan cave in 2013 that had a 96.4%
135 genetic identity with SARS-CoV-2 [4-43]. Furthermore, two sets of pangolin-
136 CoVs that were obtained from pangolins confiscated by customs in Guangxi
137 (GX) and Guangdong (GD) provinces during 2017-18 (Pang2017, Pang2018)
138 and 2019 (Pang2019) periods respectively have about 90% genetic proximity to
139 SARS-CoV-2 [44-48]. Later, pangolin samples obtained in Vietnam showed
140 similar results [49]. Likewise, a series of COVID-19 related bat-CoVs (BANAL)
141 were found in Laos [50-51]. In fact, one of the samples, BANAL-52, had an even
142 greater genetic proximity (96.8%) to SARS-CoV-2 than that of RaTG13 to SARS-
143 CoV-2.

144 A search for similarly hard M yielded CoVs associated with burrowing
145 animals such rabbits. This enigmatic association explains the true intimate
146 relationship between all COVID-19 related viruses and pangolin-CoVs since
147 pangolins are also burrowing animals [4,18-20,52-54]. The hard outer shell (M)
148 is necessary since the virus has to be able to survive longer in buried feces
149 before further transmission.
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151 While most scientists believe that COVID-19 is the result of a zoonotic
152 spillover, a better understanding of the evolution helps. The knowledge of N
153 and M proteins can make the understanding of this evolution more complete
154 as it bridges the relationship between SARS-CoV-2 and pangolin-CoV. The
155 relationship as evidenced by the pangolin molecular "footprints" can account
156 for many of the behaviors of COVID-19. The implications of this relationship
157 will be re-visited in greater detail later.
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161 One odd characteristic found in all SARS-CoV-2-related viruses and their
162 variants found thus far is the unusually hard outer shell (low M disorder) that
163 is typically found only in CoV associated with a burrowing animal. This
164 hallmark is one of the "pangolin footprints" found in all COVID-19 related
165 viruses discovered so far. The other set of footprints involve attenuations
166 arising of lesser disorder in N found in Pang2017 and, later, in the variant
167 Omicron [18-20,52-56]. The harder inner shell (N), especially in Pang2017, may
168 be also a reflection of N protecting the viral RNA in buried feces, just like M
169 [52,55].
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171 Evidence of pangolin footprints offers clues that are beginning to uncover
172 many of the mysteries of COVID-19 that are still haunting us. These include
173 questions such as: why is SARS-CoV-2 much more infectious than SARS-CoV-
174 1? Why is COVID-19 is highly infectious to this day? Why is SARS-CoV-2 less
175 virulent than SARS-CoV-1? Why is Wuhan-Hu-1 much more virulent than
176 Omicron? What is the actual structural cause of long COVID? Many of these
177 questions have remained unanswered, but the study of the M and N proteins is
178 now beginning to provide some answers from one integrated concept, namely
179 the pangolin footprints. We should not be at all surprised by the explanatory
180 prowess of the N and M proteins, as they are the most abundant proteins
181 found in the cell and virion, respectively.
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184 1.3 Long COVID

185 Yet another major mystery in COVID-19 is the presence of long COVID among
186 many patients, i.e. the persistence of symptoms long after recovery [57-58] . It
187 should also be noted that S, unlike M, is unable to account for the persistence
188 of the virus even months after the initial infection as observed by clinical
189 studies. Even as progress has been made in research to explain the mechanism
190 and cause of long COVID, long COVID has remained by and large a mystery
191 [59-64]. In this paper, we will review an alternative explanation that has
192 already been previously mentioned. This explanation involves the unusually
193 hard M found in SARS-CoV-2 that allows the virus to resist immune enzymes
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196 and enables the virus to hide in macrophages. The abnormally hard outer shell,
197 M, that protects the virion from the onslaught of the antimicrobial enzymes
198 found in saliva and mucus [19-28,40,52], is also likely to reduce the chances of
199 the elimination of viral particles via actions of the immune system. We will
200 examine literature pertaining to current knowledge of immunology that could
201 provide a potential framework for the mechanism of long COVID caused by
202 hard M. SDMs will be used to gain further insight to the potential mechanisms
203 involved.

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206 The abnormally hard outer shell, M, that protects the virion from the
207 onslaught of the antimicrobial enzymes found in saliva and mucus [19-
208 28,40,52], is also likely to reduce the chances of the elimination of viral particles
209 via actions of the immune system. Upon examination of immunological
210 principles, Shell-Disorder Models (SDMs) even go on to pinpoint the exact
211 immunological mechanisms that are likely to be hindered.
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213 214 **2. The Shell Disorder Models (SDMs): Three Closely Related Models**

215 *2.1 Three Closely Interrelated Models*

216 Three closely related models were developed using the concept of protein
217 intrinsic disorder via AI tools. Protein intrinsic disorder refers to the lack of
218 structure in an entire or part of a protein. Disorder is known to have various
219 important functions especially in protein-
220 protein/RNA/DNA/lipid/carbohydrate binding, and various tools have been
221 developed to recognize disorder regions and disordered proteins. Among the
222 first developed is PONDR[®]-VLXT, which involves the use of neural network
223 AI to recognize disordered residues given the sequence input [13-17]. PONDR[®]-
224 VLXT has been shown to be a highly appropriate tool particularly when it
225 involves viral proteins of a large variety of viruses including Ebola virus
226 (EBOV), Dengue virus (DENV), Nipah virus, and HIV [4,18-20,34-40,52,-56,65-
227 67]. PONDR[®]-VLXT is especially suited for the study of viral structural
228 proteins as it is highly sensitive in the detection of disorder in structured
229 proteins [16]. The first SDM was initiated before 2008 when PONDR[®]-VLXT
230 was used to examine the shell proteins of a variety of viruses. A useful number
231 used is percentage of intrinsic disorder (PID), which is defined as the number
232 of disordered residues predicted divided by the total number of residues in a
233 protein chain [4,65]. A disordered residue is predicted to be disordered if its
234 VLXT score is 0.5 or above. Upon comparison of the shell disorder of a fairly
235 large number of viruses, it became obvious that the outer shell of HIV,
236 especially HIV-1, has an abnormally high average disorder in its outer shells. It
237 was also discovered that HSV and HCV share this similar characteristic, even
238 though it is not as pronounced as in HIV-1 [418-20,34-40,65-67]. Since very few
239 other viruses, if any, have this characteristic, it seems to have to do with the
240 ability of the viruses to evade the immune system, and results in the absence of
241 effective vaccines for the mentioned viruses. This SDM was labeled “Viral
242 Shapeshifting” [4] and became the parent model for two other closely related
243 SDM, as seen in Figure 1. Given the behaviors of HIV, HCV, and HSV, higher
244 disorder at the outer shell can also be associated with the ability to penetrate
245 hard-to-reach places such as the brain and placenta, as in the case of the Zika
246 virus [34,35]. Protein disorder provides for greater efficiency in protein-
247 protein/DNA/RNA/lipid/glycoprotein binding [16.30-33,55,58].
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255 **Table 1.** The Three Shell Disorder Models (SDMs). SDMs were developed using
256 principles of protein intrinsic disorder applied to viral shell proteins.

Year of First	Shell Disorder	Details
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Publication	Model	
2008	Viral Shapeshifter Model (Parent)	Disorder of shell proteins was measured for a wide variety of viruses. Only very few viruses have been found to have unusually high disorder at the outer shell (HIV-1, HCV, and HSV). There is no effective vaccine yet found for the three viruses.
2012	CoV Transmission SDM	Links between modes of transmission (fecal-oral and respiratory) and N-M disorder were found.
2015	Virulence- Inner Shell Disorder Model	Strong correlation between inner shell disorder and virulence of a wide variety of viruses including DENV, EBOV, NiV, and SARS-CoV-1/2.

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Another model was developed and published in 2015 when it was discovered that there is a strong correlation between DENV virulence and disorder at the inner shell protein [34,35]. Similar correlations were found in a large variety of other viruses including NIV, CoVs, and EBOV [4,34-40,52-56,65-67]. The presence of such correlations has to do with the fact that the inner shells are often associated with replication in many viruses, and because disorder provides for greater efficiency in protein-protein/RNA/DNA/lipid/glycoprotein binding [16,30-33]. These form the basis of the Virulence-Inner Shell-Disorder Model (Table 1).

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Figure 1. Virulence-Inner SDM (Shell Disorder Model). **A.** Shells PID of DENV and SARS-CoV-2. Inner shell of DENV has been found to be correlated to virulence ($r=0.95$) [34,35]. **B.** Correlation between the SARS-related viruses and N PID. The correlation is based on estimated CFRs of SARS-CoV-1/2 and Omicron. Note: DENV and SARS-CoV-1/2 shells are not correlated. They are just placed together for illustrative purpose only.

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The third SDM was first published in 2012 [53] before MERS-CoV was discovered in 2013 [55]. The model divided CoVs into three groups, labeled A-C, that can be seen in Figure 2, with group D added during the COVID-19 pandemic [18-20,40,53,55,56]. Group D was not recognized in the initial model because there were very few CoVs that involved burrowing animals such as rabbits and pangolins at that time [4,18-16,52,53]. Before the COVID-19 pandemic, nearly all CoVs in available our database have M PIDs of at least 8% (See Figure 2 and Supplementary Table). The exceptions that have M PIDs lower than 8% are CoVs associated with burrowing animals. It was during the pandemic that it was discovered that all SARS-CoV-2-related viruses have M PIDs lower than 7% (4-6.3%) (See Figure 2 and Table 2). While the statistical differences seem small, in reality, it is actually not anything small or trivial as we will see, later, that M is the most abundant protein that encases the entire virion. Even small changes will affect the rigidity of the entire shell. This CoV-Transmission SDM invokes the same molecular principle that the Virulence-Inner SDM uses, which involves greater disorder at the inner shell that provides greater efficiency in viral replication. However, the CoV-Transmission SDM extends the principle to the levels of fecal-oral and respiratory transmission potentials, by showing that respiratory transmission is viable only when sufficient copies of the virus are shed nasally. This results in N being adequately disordered. Multivariate analysis have found strong correlation between modes of transmission and levels of M/N PIDs with statistical significance (Multivariate analysis: $p < 0.001, r \sim 0.8, N = 32$, see **Suppl. Table** for further information).

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323 **Figure 2.** CoV Transmission Shell Disorder Model (SDM) CoVs. In groups A-C, the
324 levels of respiratory/fecal-oral transmission are heavily dependent on N PID, whereas
325 those in group D have unusually low M PIDs (M disorder) that are usually associated
326 with burrowing animals such as pangolins. Group D includes all COVID-19-related
327 viruses. (Multivariate analysis: $p < 0.001, r \sim 0.8, N = 32$, see **Suppl. Table** for further
328 information)

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331 The CoV-Transmission SDM categories SARS-CoV-1 in group B consist of
332 CoVs with intermediate fecal-oral and respiratory transmission potentials.
333 Upon the publication of the original paper, the MERS-CoV outbreak took place
334 in 2012-13 when the SDM had to place MERS-CoV in group C, in which the
335 CoVs have higher and lower fecal-oral and respiratory transmission potentials
336 respectively [54]. This prediction has been reproduced clinically and
337 experimentally [4]. It is also known that MERS-CoV has long been entrenched
338 among camels, especially farmed camels, where it spreads easily by fecal-oral
339 means.
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341 3. Pangolin Footprints: Applying SDMs to SARS-CoV-2

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343 3.1.. The First Sign of a Pangolin Footprint: Abnormally Hard Shell in All SARS- 344 CoV-2-Related Viruses

345 When the CoV-Transmission SDM was first developed and implemented
346 in 2012-13, strong correlation was seen between N disorder (N PID) and the
347 modes of transmission [4,53,54]. However, statistical calculations detected a
348 small correlation between M disorder (M PID) and modes of transmission. PID

is defined as the number of disordered residues divided by the total number of residues in the protein. At that time, it was not understood why such a correlation existed. It was not until the arrival of the COVID-19 pandemic that came with a torrent of data that things began to fall in place. The CoV-Transmission SDM was applied to the Wuhan-Hu-1 as soon as the M and N proteins became available, with Wuhan-Hu-1 having N and M PIDs of 48.2% and 5.9% respectively [14,40,52-55]. Using the original model, SDM placed SARS-CoV-2 in group B, which is the same group that SARS-CoV-1 is in.

SDM did detect something highly unusual about this virus that was seldom seen in our curated database of known CoVs: the outer shell of SARS-CoV-2 is abnormally hard, i.e. has a low M PID [18-20]. As more data became available, it became clear that the odd hard outer shell was not just something that pertains only to SARS-CoV-2 but to all COVID-19-related viruses, as seen in Table 2 and Figure 2. We can see that the hard M (low M PID < 7%, Table 2) extends to all SARS-CoV-2-related viruses, including pangolin-CoVs and bat-CoVs such as RaTG13 and the Laotian bat-CoV (BANAL). Details found in the tables can also be found in previous papers [52,55-56] and the protein sequences were obtained either from UniProt [69] or NCBI-Protein [70], and the PONDR[®]-VLXT scores were obtained by inputting the sequences into PONDR[®]-VLXT [13-17]. The PIDs (percentages of intrinsic disorder) were calculated as the number of disordered residues divided by the total number of protein in a protein chain [4,65-67].

Table 2. N/M PIDs and Sequence Similarities of COVID-19 Related Viruses CoVs with SARS-CoV-1 and Non-SARS-CoV-2-related Bat-CoVs as references. It should be noted that BA1 was the initial Omicron. **At least two Delta subvariants have been detected by SDMs.**

Coronavirus	Sequence Similarity M (%)	M PID (%)	Accession: UniProt (U); GenBank (G)	Sequence Similarity N (%)	N PID (%)	Accession UniProt (U); GenBank(G)
SARS-CoV-1	90.5	8.6	P59596(U)	90.5	50.2	P59595(U)
Civet-SARS-CoV	90.1	8.6	Q3ZTE9(U)	90.01	49.1	Q3ZTE4(U)
Laotian Bat-CoV	-	6.0±0.2	-	-	48.3±0.2	-
[Banal-52]	98.7	6.3	UAY13220.1	99.3	48.2	UAY13225.1
[Banal-103]	98.7	5.9	UAY13232.1	99.1	48.5	UAY13257.1
[Banal-236]	99.1	4.1	UAY13256.1	99.3	48.5	UAY1326.1
Pangolin-CoV	-	5.6±0.9	-	-	46.6±1.6	-
2019	98.2	6.3	QIG55948(G)	98	48.7	QIG55953(G)
2018	97.7	4.5	QIQ54051(G)	93.8	46.3	QIQ54056(G)
2017	98.2	5.9	QIA48617(G)	94	44.9	QIA48630(G)
				93.32	46.5	QIA48656(G)
SARS-CoV-2						
Wuhan-Hu-1	100	5.9	YP009724393(G)	100	48.2	YP009724397(G)
Delta					47.1±0.5	
Delta1	99.1	5.9±0.01	QUX81285(G)		46.8	QYM89997(G)
Delta2	99.1	5.9	QUX81285(G)		47.5	QYM89845(G)
		5.9		99.1		-
Omicron	-		-		44.5±0.4	UFO692871(G)
Omicron BA1	98.7	5.7±0.4	UFO59282(G)	-	44.8	WIL50325
Omicron XBB	99.1	5.4	WBI50320(G)	98.6	44.2	

		5.9		98.2		
Bat-CoV		11.2±15			47.7±0.9	
RATG13	99.6	4.1	QHR63303(G)	99.1	48.5	QHR63308(G)
Bat 512	35.5	15.3	Q0Q463(U)	29.4	46.5	Q0Q462(U)
HKU3	91	7.7	Q3LZX9(U)	89.6	48	Q3LZX4(U)
HKU4	42.7	16.4	A3EXA0(U)	51.1	48.5	A3EXA1(U)
HKU5	44.7	11.8	A3EXD6(U)	47.9	47.1	A3EXD7(U)

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It was only after the arrival of the pandemic, which came with new data, that we realized that group D has to be added, and there was a good reason why we missed group C in the beginning. A retrospective search for similarly low M PID can only be found in CoVs associated with burrowing animals such as rabbits [18-19,55]. Because there were very few such CoVs in the public database before the pandemic, the CoV-Transmission SDM was inevitably incomplete at that time. As according to our previously published papers [19,20], it also became obvious that the hard M was responsible for the high transmissibility among humans by protecting the virus from the myriad of anti-microbial enzymes found in the mucus and saliva [18-20,40,45,52]. As a result, the host will shed large amounts of infectious particles nasally and orally. There is also reason to suspect that the abnormally hard M may have a lot to do with long COVID [40], as it is possible that the host immune system may often have difficulties destroying and getting rid of the viral particles.

3.2. Signs of Attenuation: Another Pangolin Footprint

The three SDMs present us with a set of tools that are able to create a wide range of specific predictions about SARS-CoV-2 and its closely related relatives. Just like the SDM's prediction was applied to MERS, the predictions have shown consistency when applied to experimental and clinical data. Figure 2 summarizes an example of the application of the Virulence-Inner SDM to COVID-19 that is consistent with clinical and experimental data. A strong correlation can be found between COVID-19 virulence and N PID. Using case fatality rate (CFR) as a benchmark for virulence, we are able to see that the CFR varies with the N disorder (N PID) with SARS-CoV-1 having the highest CFR of about 10%, followed by the non-Omicron SARS-CoV-2 variants, and then Omicron (Figure 1B). Even without using CFR, the Virulence-Inner SDM makes specific predictions about the levels of virulence of the SARS-related viruses and SARS-CoV-1. SARS-CoV-1 is predicted to be of higher virulence given its N PID of 50%, followed by Wuhan-Hu-1 (N PID: 48.2%), and the other non-Omicron variants (Delta N PID~47.1±0.5%). Omicron (N PID~44.5±0.4%) is the least virulent thus far [40,52,55-56]. It should also be known that CFR is just one measure of the link. As we shall see, it has been complemented with viral titer and cell/tissue studies. The SDMs are able to pinpoint the mechanisms that account for the predictions. In this case of COVID-19 virulence, the higher the N disorder, the greater the efficiency in viral replication that the virus is able to acquire, as N is intimately involved in the replication process and greater disorder provides for better protein-protein/RNA/DNA/Lipid/glycoprotein interactions.

3.3 Pangolin Footprints: Implications and Manifestations

Two important predictions seen in Figure 1B that have been reproduced are that Omicron and Pangolin-2017 (Pang2017) are attenuated based on their low N PIDs. This prediction was first mentioned in a publication in 2020 [14] and later reproduced in at least two laboratories. Omicron, however, did not emerge until November 2021. When the first Omicron sequence became available, it was found that the Omicron subvariant, BA1, has an N of 44.7%, which is very close to that of Pang2017 at 44.8% [20,52,55-56]. Just as Pang2017 was predicted to be attenuated. Omicron or, at least, BA1 has to be considered attenuated. It was later shown that all Omicron subvariants have similar N PID, with the later ones being even lower (XBB.1.16, N PID: 44.2%). Both Pang2017 and Omicron have been clinically and experimentally shown to be

431 attenuated with lower viral titer [40,51,74-79]. Interestingly, in contrast,
432 Pang2019 N PID resembles that of non-Omicron variants, and, not
433 coincidentally, its virulence and viral titers do not resemble those of Omicron
434 or Pang2017 [80-82].
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436 3.5. Implications and Manifestations: Infectivity and Virulence

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438 Figure 3A summarizes the implications of SDMs and the effects of
439 different N and M PIDs on the manifestation of COVID-19. Since SARS-CoV-1
440 (SARS1) has a higher N PID (~50%) and produces more viral particles,
441 especially in the vital organs, but because its M is not as hard (M PID ~ 9%)
442 [4], it offers less resistance to the onslaught of the salivary and mucosal anti-
443 microbial enzymes and yet produces sufficient infectious particles for viable
444 respiratory transmission. However, SARS-CoV-2 presents a different story. The
445 Wuhan-Hu1 strain has a somewhat lesser N disorder (N PID ~ 48%) but a
446 much lesser M disorder (M PID ~ 5.7%) [40]. According to SDMs, the virus will
447 replicate well even in vital organs, but not as efficiently as SARS-CoV-1. Even
448 though Wuhan-Hu-1 does not replicate in large quantities in contrast to SARS-
449 CoV-1, the patient sheds more infectious particles because its harder M offers
450 more resistance to the anti-microbial enzymes in the saliva and mucus [40,52].
451 For this reason, Wuhan-Hu-1 is virulent, but not as much as SARS-CoV-1. On
452 the other hand, it is much more infectious than the latter, due to the immense
453 amount of shedding. Omicron presents a different scenario with a similarly
454 low M PID (~5.7%) but much lower N PID (~44.5%). With these, the SDMs
455 predict low virulence but high infectivity, even if lower than Wuhan-Hu-1. All
456 these predictions have been reproduced experimentally and clinically
457 [52,55,71-82].

458 Figure 3A describes the underlying mechanism of how differences in N
459 and M disorder affect manifestation of the virus, especially with respect to
460 virulence and transmission. SARS-CoV-1 (SARS1) spreads efficiently via
461 respiratory mode with greater virulence, but not as efficiently as SARS-CoV-2
462 (SARS2). SDMs attribute these properties to higher N and M PIDs (N PID: 50%,
463 M PID: 9%) in contrast to those of SARS-CoV-2. Figure 3B illustrates the
464 mechanism of COVID-19 attenuation via pangolins with analogy from Nipah
465 virus [4,18,32,33,83].

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SARS-CoV-1

SARS-CoV-2 (Wuhan)

SARS-CoV-2 (Omicron)

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Figure 3. Effects of M and N disorder on virulence and infectivity. **A.** Effects of M and N disorder on virus replication. **B.** Effects of environment on virulence. SARS-CoV-1 produces high quantities of viral particles, especially in vital organs, because of its high N disorder, but by the time they reach the nasal and oral cavity, many have already been eliminated by mucosal and salivary antimicrobial enzymes as a result of its lower M PID. SARS-CoV-2, on the other hand, produces less particles in the entire respiratory system, but more particles are able to resist the antimicrobial enzymes because of its hard M, and, therefore, its patients shed more particles. NiV is highly virulent when it is spread directly from bats, whereas the variant that had pigs as an intermediate host was less virulent. The inner shell disorder of the latter was observed. Similar observations were made for SARS-CoV-1/2.

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505 While Figure 3A summarizes the mechanisms in which infectiousness and
506 virulence is modulated, Figure 3B shows the evolutionary implications of the
507 mechanisms described. The reason that SARS-CoV-1 was more virulent is
508 likely the result of its shortness of time the virus was in its intermediary host,
509 civet cat, before the zoonotic transmission to humans. In contrast, the Nipah
510 virus (NiV) is usually highly virulent when the transmission to human is
511 directly from bats, as in the cases seen in Bangladesh and India. Meanwhile,
512 the 1999-2000 outbreak involved infection of humans via pigs as intermediary
513 hosts, and the human CFR was about 50%, compared to the 75% CFR in the
514 cases from India-Bangladesh [4,33,36,83].

515 The fact that it was discovered via PONDR[®]-VLXT that the disorder of
516 inner shell proteins of the virus from the Malaysia outbreak was lower than
517 those from the Bangladesh-India outbreaks is consistent with the prediction of
518 the Virulence-Inner SDM and disorder observations of viruses from the same
519 family. Attenuation of the virus came during its infection of pigs, in which
520 fecal-oral transmission is the most convenient route in a farm environment.
521 The hardening of the inner shell protein poses several advantages. Firstly, the
522 fecal-oral route does not necessitate higher disorder in its inner shell protein
523 and greater disorder requires greater energy, which is a waste if not utilized.
524 Secondly, a harder inner shell offers some extra protection to the viral genome.
525 Bat CoVs in general have higher N disorder, possibly arising from the need for
526 certain levels of respiratory transmission potentials because of the behavior,
527 involving flights, of bats. Respiratory diseases, such as avian influenza, have
528 been known to spread between birds during flight [84-87]. There is therefore no
529 reason not to believe that respiratory viruses such as CoVs can spread between
530 between bats during flights. SDMs support this notion when we see IBV, which
531 is an avian coronavirus, has among the highest N PIDs and higher N PID is
532 associated with higher respiratory transmission.(Figure 2). Indeed, as we will
533 see later, bat-CoV N PID are usually higher than those of most other CoVs.
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535 Given the generally lower N PID and, thus, virulence, it makes more
536 sense if the precursor SARS-CoV-2 was deeply entrenched in an intermediary
537 animal host. There are important reasons to believe that pangolins were
538 involved. A smoking gun can be found in the abnormally hard M found in all
539 COVID-19 related viruses that suggests a burrowing animal. The presence of
540 SARS-CoV-2-related pangolin-CoVs are apparently widespread in Southern
541 China and Southeast Asia, as evidenced by the discoveries of pangolin-CoVs in
542 Guangxi, Guangdong, and Vietnam [42-49]. Figure 3B reminds us that
543 pangolin is a likely reservoir, with Pangolin-CoVs moving to and fro among
544 bats, humans, and pangolins.
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546 3.6. *Physiological Mechanisms Allow Dichotomy between Virulence and Infectivity:* 547 *Mucociliary Clearance (MCC)*

548 It has to be understood that the CoV-Transmission SDM revolves around
549 the need to have sufficient concentration of infectious particles for the virus to
550 have viable respiratory transmissibility. This can be facilitated by an
551 abnormally hard M, more disorder in N, or both, since a harder M makes the
552 virion more resistant to damage arising from the anti-microbial enzymes found
553 in the mucus and saliva [21-28], whereas a more disordered N could induce
554 more efficient viral replication as the result of more effective protein-protein
555 binding. The latter is again used in the Virulence-Inner SDM, in which higher
556 N disorder helps rapid replication of viral particles, especially in vital organs.
557 How do the two factors interplay to allow us consistency among the various
558 SDMs? A part of the answer has been explained in Figure 3A, which
559 summarizes how virulence and infectiousness are intertwined. It does not,
560 however, tell the whole story, especially with regard to how the physiology of
561 the host helps in the entire process.
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563 Knowledge of molecular physiology has allowed us to understand the
564 roles that the respiratory system plays in the entire transmission process.
565 Mucociliary Clearance (MCC) or Mucociliary Escalator is of particular interest
566 [88-91]. It encompasses a body of knowledge that describes how the respiratory

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system expels foreign bodies, including viruses and bacteria, via a mechanism known as MCC. MCC is a sophisticated network of hairy ciliated cells covered with mucus that transport foreign bodies away from the lungs towards upper respiratory regions to be shed, as seen in Figure 4. During the transportation process, the particle is exposed to antimicrobial enzymes in mucus.

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Figure 4. The Mucociliary Escalator/Clearance (MCC) System. MCC consists of a network of mucus-covered structures found in ciliary cells. These mucus-covered structures would push foreign materials away from the lungs towards the mouth and nasal cavity. MCC is absent in the lungs, where mucus is replaced by surfactants. About 2/3 of foreign matters in the lungs are expelled into MCC. The rest are engulfed by macrophages or remain in the lungs.

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The three main types of cells in the respiratory tract are ciliate cells, goblet cells, and basal cells. We know that the ciliate cells, which are mucus-coated cells with hair-like structures that are used to move particles away from the lungs, while goblet cells produce the mucus [80]. In contrast, however, the lungs have different types of cells that don't contain mucus. It is likely that the antimicrobial enzymes in mucus and saliva are too harsh for the delicate function of the lungs. Instead, the mucus is replaced by surfactant. The cells found in the lungs are alveolar type I cells (AT1), alveolar type II (pneumocytes, AT2), and macrophages. AT1 secretes surfactants [91-92]. While surfactants are known to have some antimicrobial properties, they are incomparable to the myriad of antimicrobial enzymes found in the mucus.

Given these physiological mechanisms, we can now understand how the host body modulates in the spread and virulence of SARS-CoV-1/2 as seen in Figure 3. When SARS-CoV-1 infects a patient, the greater N disorder allows for the rapid replication of greater quantity of viral particles throughout the respiratory system. The particles are, however, subjected to MCC, in which the particles are swept upwards towards the nasal cavity, but by the time it reaches the nostril, much of the infectious particles are eliminated or damaged due to the comparatively less rigid outer shell, M. The particles that are produced in the lungs tell a different story. Experiments have shown that the lungs do partially participate in the MCC process by pushing 2/3 of foreign particles into the respiratory tract [93]. Since 1/3 of the particles originally in the lungs stay in the lungs, the remaining particles could pose a danger to the patient by damaging the lungs, especially when there are many of them. SARS-CoV-2, on the other hand, produces a more moderate amounts of particles throughout the respiratory system, and many of the particles that are transported to the nostril via MCC remain undamaged, unlike in the cases of SARS-CoV-2, since the former has an abnormally hard M.

3.7. *Phylogenetic Trees Using M Reveal a More Intimate Relationship Between Pangolin-CoVs and SARS-CoV-2: Another Sign of a Pangolin Footprint*

We have seen that a hard M is the hallmark of all thus-known COVID-19 viruses. Being hard or ordered usually entails a more conserved protein. Based on this, M is very likely to be highly conserved among all COVID-19 related viruses. Such a feature makes M more ideal for phylogenetic studies, as it is known that recombinations could cause gross errors in phylogenetic calculations. Interestingly, phylogenetic calculations yielded results that are different from those using the entire genome or other proteins [41-48,52,55]. Figure 5A,C uses M to show that pangolin-CoVs have a much closer relationship to SARS-CoV-2, not seen when other protein such N (Figure 5B) or entire genome is used.

Figure 5A is different from Figure 5C as they involve slightly different algorithms. In any case, both show that pangolin-CoVs have intimate relationships with SARS-CoV-2. It is interesting to note that the two viruses that have the greatest sequence similarities to SARS-CoV-2 are bat-CoVs, RaTG13 and BANAL-52, with 96.1% and 96.8% respectively [51-52]. What is intriguing, however, is that in Figure 3A, it can be seen that BANAL-52 and Pang2019 have the similarly closest relationship to SARS-CoV-2, in contrast to RaTG13. How can this be when RaTG13 has a 96.1% sequence identity to SARS-CoV-2, compared to about 90% for Pang2019? Sequence identity does not offer the full picture because of the possibility of recombination occurring. Furthermore, phylogenetic genetic algorithms tend to make mistakes when recombination had taken place [94]. The abnormally hard M found in all COVID-19-related viruses entails a structural and genetic conservation, which means that the likelihood of any recombination having taken place is much lower. Therefore, we believe that Figure 5A,C presents the most accurate phylogenetic study by avoiding the chances of recombination.

Yet another odd feature can be seen in Figure 5C, where Omicron is more closely related to the pangolin-CoVs than to the other variants [40,52,55]. While this may seem odd, we know that Omicron itself is shrouded in mystery. When Omicron was first sequenced, it was found to have mutations that are unlike any other variants. The question that quickly arises is: Where has Omicron been hiding all along? [95]. Why didn't the medical and scientific community notice it if it was in the human population? There were a few suggestions. A few scientists suggested that the virus was hiding in a small group of immunocompromised people such HIV or cancer patients [96]. Others have suggested that the virus had been hiding in an animal such as rat or pangolin. One paper has suggested that Omicron had been hiding among mice based on the mutations of its S and mouse ACE-2 [96]. Disorder studies on Omicron do suggest that it could be hiding in a burrowing animal such as pangolin as the first Omicron variant BA1 had an even harder M than other SARS-CoV-2 variants (M PIDs: 5.4% Vs 5.8%) [55]. The idea that Omicron had been hiding in mice actually does not contradict the suggestion in the previous statement since mice are also burrowing animals. A complication arises, however, when we examine the evolution of mice and rats. While rats and mice dwell in burrows in the countryside, rats and mice in the urban settings have evolved to live in the homes of human (Schmidt-Holmes et al) [97]. Therefore, depending on the species, they could have characteristics of both burrowing and non-burrowing animals. The phylogenetic tree (Figure 5C) that shows an unusually close relationship between Omicron and pangolin-CoVs, in contrast to the other variants, adds an important clue towards solving the puzzle. The phylogenetic tree is suggesting that it was literally hiding within a population of a burrowing animal such as pangolins.

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684 **Figure 5. A** CoV Phylogenetic Study Trees Using M. **A.** Phylogenetic study of CoVs using M via CLUSTAL OMEGA [89].
685 **B.** Phylogenetic study of CoVs using N via CLUSTAL OMEGA [98-99] . **C.** Phylogenetic study of COVID-19-related
686 viruses using M (via CLUSTALW [100]). Viruses related to SARS-CoV-2/1 are shaded in blue in (A) and (B).

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4. The Shell Disorder Models and Reproducibility: M and N Proteins

4.1. The Problem with the S Protein: Limitations and Potentials

When COVID-19 first struck in Wuhan it spread globally with a ferocity not seen since SAR-CoV-1, despite efforts to control it. Almost immediately, many scientists began to zero in on S as the protein responsible for its high infectivity [9-11]. A computational model suggested that the SARS-CoV-2 S binds more efficiently to the ACE-2 receptor than SARS-CoV-1 [9-11]. Furthermore, a specific polybasic sequence known as the furin cleavage (FCS) can only be found in SARS-CoV-2 but not in the COVID-19-related bat-CoVs and pangolin-CoV and SARS-CoV-1 [101-103]. Many scientists hailed S, as well as FCS, as the holy grail of COVID-19 transmissibility and virulence knowledge [102-103].

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The S protein has been widely studied [104] since it plays important roles with many implications. It is intimately involved in viral entry, which presents an opportunity for the discovery of drugs and vaccines that block the attachment of the virus to the host cells [104]. Furthermore, being a surface protein, it is being widely studied for the way its mutations help evade the host immune system. It is therefore not difficult to see why S is the most studied CoV protein. S is, however, so intensively studied that it is easy to get the impression that it is the only protein that matters, or that no other CoV protein exists. This paradigm is, of course, nonsensical as it violates a basic tenet of biochemistry: each protein plays individual but important roles [105].

Even in the debate involving COVID's origin, many scientists seem to imply that the secret of COVID infectiousness and virulence lies in the S protein and that the moment that the secret of S is unlocked, the origin of

715 COVID-19 will be uncovered as well [102-103]. Contrary to the popular notion,
716 there is mounting clinical and experimental evidence that the S protein may
717 not be the main underlying cause of COVID-19 infectiousness and virulence.
718 One major piece of evidence for this lies in a comprehensive clinical study
719 conducted by Wolfel et al [29]. In this study, it was found that COVID-19
720 patients shed much more infectious particles than SARS-CoV-1 patients. If we
721 look closely, the question that comes to mind is: why does SARS-CoV-2 need
722 much more particles to be more infectious if its S has a 10 or 1000 times [9-11]
723 greater binding affinity to ACE-2 than the latter? Keeping in mind that it
724 requires much more energy to produce these extra infectious particles and
725 nature does not, as a rule, usually waste energy to do redundant things. One
726 could, however, attempt to get around this paradox by claiming that the S
727 affinity to ACE-2 is responsible for the more rapid replication of the virus.
728 Unfortunately, this suggestion contradicts what we know about the life-cycle
729 of the virus, as viral entry represents only an initial stage of a long series of
730 process that includes RNA replication, protein production, assembly,
731 packaging, and the budding of viral particles [106-109].
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733 There are those who suggest that it is possible that SARS-CoV-1 S binds
734 more efficiently to the ACE-2 in cells in the lower respiratory in contrast to
735 SARS-CoV-2 [12]. There are a number of issues that arise when such an
736 argument is made. Firstly, the argument is made without any considering
737 current physiological knowledge, namely the Mucociliary Clearance system
738 (MCC), which allows viral particles produced throughout the respiratory
739 system to be transported upwards towards the nasal area so that they could be
740 expelled and shed [88-91]. Secondly, to our knowledge, attempts to reproduce
741 the argument involving SARS-CoV-1 S and ACE-2 has not been conducted
742 experimentally, probably, because of the current difficulty in obtaining the now
743 extinct SARS-CoV-1 to conduct comparative experiment alongside SARS-CoV-
744 2. There are, however, also similar arguments made to account for the
745 differences in virulence of Omicron and non-Omicron variants Hui et al [78].
746 This difference is that COVID-19 pandemic provides us with a deluge of
747 clinical and experimental data. In fact, attempts to reproduce this argument has
748 been made, which we will discuss at length later.
749

750 The clinical study of Wolfel et. al. [29] is just the tip of the iceberg, as there
751 is also a deluge of other evidence that shows that the nature of S is not what
752 many scientists have made it out to be. Nor does S alone provide for a coherent
753 conceptual framework of COVID-19 infectiousness and virulence, unlike M
754 and N. This is also the case with long COVID. We will examine these in greater
755 details in later sections. This is not to say that S is unimportant or that it does
756 not play any part in infectiousness or virulence. It is important, but we must
757 also fully comprehend its true potential and limitation. A more complete
758 understanding of the true limitations and potentials of S will come when we
759 study other important proteins such as N and M more thoroughly, which is
760 challenging even if the majority of research is oriented towards S.
761

762 *4.2. SDMs and Reproducibility*

763 We have seen that SDMs are highly reproducible by their ability to
764 accurately predict and explain certain phenomena that are otherwise difficult
765 to account for. Unlike alternative explanations, they are explained in a coherent
766 manner using a logical and unified paradigm that is consistent with current
767 knowledge of physiology and biochemistry [52]. There is also important
768 clinical and experimental evidence that reproduces many of the predictions of
769 SDMs.

770 While a previous experiment was not able to detect any statistical
771 difference in the ability of SARS-CoV-2 to last on various surfaces under
772 presence of light when compared to SARS-CoV-1, Riddell et al. [21] conducted
773 a similar experiment, devoid of light, and found that SARS-CoV-2 lasts much
774 longer on external surfaces than the control CoVs. SDMs predict that SARS-
775 CoV-2 is more persistent than most virus as its unusually hard M protects
776 against the environment and harsh antimicrobial enzymes, and this experiment
777 reaffirms SARS-CoV-2's resilience in the absence of light.

778 Reproducibility of SDMs is not confined to computational and
779 experimental research, but also extends to clinical studies. One such study
780 involved an investigation into the infectiousness of SARS-CoV-19. It was found

781 that COVID-19 patients shed a much larger amount of infectious particles than
782 the 2003-SARS patients [29]. This contradicts all other paradigms set forth. For
783 instance, if S is fully responsible and has a much greater affinity for human
784 ACE-2, why does SARS-CoV-2 need to expunge such higher quantities of
785 particles in order to be more infectious? SDMs provide for a much more
786 elegant explanation: the virus is more resistant to the salivary and mucosal
787 anti-microbial enzymes because of the abnormally hard SARS-CoV-2 outer
788 shell (low M PID). This clinical observation raises more questions than it
789 answers. More specifically, how is the virus able to make the host expunge
790 such a large amount of particles without being more virulent to the body? If we
791 assume that the body is shedding more viral particles because it is producing
792 more virus copies, then vital organs such as the lungs should be flooded with
793 the virus, thus making the latter more dangerous, but this is apparently not
794 happening in the case of COVID-19.

795 Adding to the paradox, Ogando et al. [79] found that SARS-CoV-1 has a
796 higher viral growth VERO-E6 cells than SARS-CoV-2 under the same
797 conditions. Even if this is consistent with the greater pathogenesis of SARS-
798 CoV-2, how do we then reconcile this result with the previously mentioned
799 clinical observation? If SARS-CoV-2 S has a 10 or 1000 times [9-11] greater
800 affinity for ACE-2 than the affinity between SARS-CoV-1 S and ACE-2, how is
801 this possible? It seems that we need to look elsewhere for answers by
802 examining N and M more closely. The SDMs explain that the reason that
803 SARS-CoV-1 is producing higher levels of particles has to do with the higher N
804 disorder that allows greater efficiencies in its replication process but,
805 conversely, lesser infectious particles are shed by the body as the higher M PID
806 does not provide sufficient protection against the antimicrobial enzymes.

807 Yet another enigma involves long COVID [110-111], and SDMs are able to
808 explain the persistence of the virus among COVID-19 patients even months
809 after infection. Again, we return to the theme of hard M that protects the virus
810 from antimicrobial enzymes. This time the focus is not only on mucosal and
811 salivary enzymes as in the case of infectivity, but also on antimicrobial
812 enzymes in the immune system. Further discussion on the antimicrobial
813 enzymes found in the immune system can be found in the long COVID section
814 below.
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816 4.3 More Reproducibility: Omicrons and Pangolin-CoVs

817
818 There are many other predictions that SDMs make involving N and M.
819 One such prediction pertains to pangolin-CoV. When SDMs were applied to
820 pangolin-CoVs, it became obvious that the 2017 pangolin-CoV (Pang2017)
821 isolate from Guangxi is attenuated because of its low N PID (~44%) [40,52,55-
822 56]. There are several implications for this finding. If this or a similar virus had
823 entered the human population, it is likely that it would have easily moved
824 quietly among humans as a mild cold without the notice of the medical
825 communities [18]. The predicted attenuation has been independently
826 reproduced by several laboratories [52,55,74-77]. Animals models have seen
827 milder manifestation of symptoms upon Pang2017 infection, in contrast of the
828 Wuhan-Hu-1 strain. The SDMs prediction pertaining to Pang2017 was
829 published before the arrival of Omicron.
830

831 Omicron was first detected in South Africa around November 2021.
832 Omicron was clinically and, later, experimentally observed to be milder than
833 previous variants [71-78]. Once again, SDMs have much to say. Based on the
834 initial Omicron subvariant, BA.1, the N and M PIDs are 43.65% and 5.4%,
835 which are both lower than previous variants [49]. The smaller than usual M
836 PID (5.9% vs. 5.4%) could suggest that the virus had a recent origin involving a
837 burrowing animal, whereas the lower N PID predicts that Omicron is likely
838 attenuated to similar levels as Pang2017. The prediction involving N PIDs was
839 experimentally replicated when it was shown that the viral growth of VERO-
840 E6 cells infected by Pang2017 and Omicron respectively are very similar, and
841 when it was shown that the viral damage on cells by the two viruses are
842 similar [55]. This presents evidence of further reproducibilities for both
843 Pang2017 and Omicron. Omicron has also been shown to be attenuated with
844 lower growth than Wuhan-Hu-1 under viral titration [55,75,77,79].
845

846 The correlations between N disorder and viral titer or virulence can be
847 found in SARS-CoV-2 related virus data that include Pang2019 [71-73,75] and
848 the Laotian bats-CoV (BANAL) [50-51]. Furthermore, while Pang2017 has been
849 predicted and reaffirmed to be attenuated, this is not the case with Pang2019.
850 Instead, SDMs have to predict Pang2019 to be non-attenuated with its N PID at
851 48.2% [18,52,55-56]. Huo et al. [81] were able to obtain levels of viral titer from
852 Pang2019 similar to those of Wuhan-Hu-1 in VERO-E6 cells. Several
853 laboratories were also able to independently observe that Pang2019 is able to
854 inflict severe disease in at least one strain of mice. In contrast, virulence was
855 not observed in Pang2017 [55,74-79]. All these are again consistent with the
856 predictions of SDMs. We know that all of these SARS-CoV-2 related viruses do
857 not possess FCS, unlike SARS-CoV-2. The question then becomes: how does
858 Pang2019 possess similar infectivity and virulence as SARS-CoV-2 without
859 FCS, when FCS-mutant non-Omicron SARS-CoV-2 is largely not transmissible
860 among ferrets?
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862 *4.7. Measuring Virulence Using CFR, Animal Models and Cell/Tissue Damage* 863 *Observation*

864 While Figure 1 shows correlation between Inner Shell Disorder and CFR, it must
865 be admitted that CFR is not necessarily the most ideal representation of virulence for at
866 least two reasons. Firstly, CFR figures are often extrapolated out of necessity [103].
867 Secondly, CFR is applied only to human, not animals. Furthermore, virulence may vary
868 among different animals even within a single virus or variant. There are, however,
869 other methods of measuring virulence such as animal models, viral titration and
870 indications of cell/tissue damage after infection. We have mentioned some of the
871 animal models. It must be noted that attenuation or aggressiveness of SARS-CoV-2
872 variants, Pang2017-CoV and Pang2019-CoV were reproduced by viral titrations,
873 animal models and inspections of cell/tissue damage after infecting cells or animals
874 were conducted by at least two independent laboratories for each virus or variant
875 [55,74-79]. The animal models included, at least, hamsters and several strains of mice.
876 In addition, the severity of Pang2019-CoV infection was also observed in pangolins
877 under laboratory conditions [80-82]. It can also be argued that a SARS-CoV-2 related
878 virus may infect different types of cells in different manner, which could potentially
879 make interpretation of viral titration data more challenging. This is related to the
880 argument made by some scientists that SARS-CoV-1 could infect the lower respiratory
881 tract more efficiently in comparison to SARS-CoV-2. There are, however, hints that the
882 arguments may not present a great difficulty in the interpretation of viral titration data.
883 Viral titrations have been made a variety of cells including Vero E6, Calu3 and Caco2
884 [77]. The data show subtle but definite differences in the viral titers using the three
885 different cell lines that is the result of differences in S-ACE-2 binding mechanism. The
886 differences, however, are not so huge that it would make interpretation of viral titration
887 data challenging as the variations viral titers among cell types are not great and follows
888 a trend. Besides, as we see later, the S of SARS-CoV-2 related viruses typically
889 become quickly more efficient to binding to the S of different cell types after several
890 passages. With all these in mind, it is possible to present a consistent picture of
891 virulence nad infectivity. In fact, a previous paper [55] was able to find a positive
892 correlation between virulence and N PIDs based on a combination of data from viral
893 titer, animal model and cell plaques.
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896 **5. Comparative Roles of S, M, and N Proteins**

897 *5.1. The S Protein, Omicron, and Pangolins*

898 We have seen that the use of S is unable to explain some crucial
899 experimental and clinical data. This just the tip of the iceberg, as there is more
900 experimental and clinical data that S alone simply cannot explain or account
901 for and, thus far, attempts to do so are not reproducible, or can be shown to be
902 inherently flawed as we have argued. There are also important biological
903 reasons for this. For us to understand this, we need to examine the basic
904 fundamental biology of the virus. While S is definitely an important protein in
905 terms of viral entry, there is no fundamental reason that S should be the most
906 important protein in COVID-19 infectiousness and virulence, as much as many
907 scientists would like to believe. Viral entry, though important, is just the first
908 of the many steps in the virus' life-cycle [109]. It must be emphasized that

909 SARS-CoV-2 encodes 19 proteins, even though not all are major proteins [109].
910 S is not the only major protein, and neither is it the most abundant protein. On
911 the contrary, the N and M are the most abundant major structural proteins
912 found in the cell and virion respectively [96-100]. For this reason alone, we
913 should not be surprised if N and M have greater influence on the infectivity
914 and pathogenesis of the virus.

915 Further sets of perplexing evidence that contradict the “S-alone”
916 paradigm can be found in the data that pertains to pangolin-CoVs and
917 Omicron. We need to keep in mind that all variants of SARS-CoV-2 have FCS
918 that is absent in all COVID-19-related bat and pangolin viruses. Many scientists
919 thought that they have found FCS to be the true cause of COVID-19
920 infectiousness and virulence when it was found that SARS-CoV-2 with FCS
921 intact is more aggressive in respiratory cells, in contrast to the FCS-mutated
922 one, by promoting cell to cell fusion. Furthermore, it has been shown that while
923 non-Omicron SARS-CoV-2 wild-type can be transmitted experimentally via
924 aerosol between hamsters, no transmission was seen when FCS-mutant was
925 used on ferrets [113]. Again, how can this be the case, given that pangolin-CoV
926 has no FCS and is easily transmitted between hamsters [74-75,81] ?
927

928 *5.2. The S and Omicron Conundrum*

929
930 When Omicron arrived, it presented an enigma by being infectious and
931 yet attenuated. How did Omicron achieve its attenuation given that it has FCS
932 just like all other variants? Animal studies have shown that rats are unable to
933 transmit via aerosol in the laboratory. How could this be so when Omicron has
934 been clinically shown to be highly infectious? More importantly, how can this
935 be happen when Omicron has efficient FCS [114-115], in which its presence in
936 other variants has been shown to induce greater transmissibility in ferrets
937 [113]? These discrepancies point to the probability that other factors are in play.
938 In fact, all these, as we have shown, are consistent with the workings of N and
939 M, as summarized in Figure 5.

940 An attempt to get around this “S-Omicron” paradox is the hypothesis that
941 claims Omicron infects the cells in the upper respiratory system more easily
942 than the lungs. Hui et al. [78] were able to isolate bronchial and lung tissues,
943 which were infected with Omicron and previous COVID-19 variants. They
944 were able to qualitatively see the greater presence of viral particles and
945 concluded that Omicron is attenuated because it replicates more easily in the
946 lungs than in the bronchi. There are, however, a number of problems with this
947 interpretation. Firstly, this observation has not, to our knowledge, been
948 reproduced in other laboratories. In fact, several laboratories have observed
949 efficient replications in both lungs and upper respiratory systems [77,116-117].
950 Furthermore, several other independent laboratories have noticed that many
951 non-variants of Omicron are even more adapted to the human ACE-2 than the
952 non-Omicron variants [116-118]. If this is the case, why hasn't Omicron
953 achieved greater virulence and infectivity like its predecessors?
954

955 *5.3. Evidence of the Different Roles of N and M in Experimental Data*

956
957 The story is actually even more complicated than what Hui et al. had
958 envisaged [78]. In reality, the N and M proteins, together with knowledge of
959 MCC, provide a more consistent and reproducible explanation for their results.
960 In our previous publications, we have shown that the initial waves of Omicron
961 ha lower M PIDs than previous variants. This feature is likely a tell-tale sign of
962 its recent interactions with a burrowing animal, possibly, the pangolin. In any
963 case, it explains why Hui et al. were able to see more viral particles in the
964 bronchi. It is because Omicron is more resistant to the anti-microbial mucosal
965 enzymes that it encounters as it is being transported upwards by the hair-like
966 structures in the network of mucus-covered ciliary cells. The lung has no ciliary
967 cells or mucus but has surfactants that, even though it is anti-microbial, is not
968 as harsh, unlike the variety of enzymes present. The apparent lack of viral
969 particles is likely an indication of particles still trapped in the tissues as there
970 would not be MCC to bring it to the top in the lungs [88-92] .
971

972 Viral titrations were also made using Omicron, Delta, and Wuhan-Hu-1 in
973 lungs and bronchial tissues in the above-mentioned experiment. The data were
974 used to support the hypothesis of differentiated replication of Omicron in the

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lungs and bronchi. In one of our previous articles, we managed to use their data to perform multivariate analysis (Figure 6). The viral titration data were taken from publicly available paper of Hui et al, while N and M PIDs based on variants and sub-variants were taken from our curated disorder database (Table 2). Regression (Multivariate) Analysis was performed using R package. The regression analysis provides us with the correlations between viral titer and N/M PIDs is measured as correlation coefficients (r) or coefficients of determination (r^2). The total n (sample size) for the entire statistical experiment as seen in Figure 6 is 24 ($p < 0.01$, $n = 24$, $r^2 \sim 0.9$). Statistical results were computed using R package that is available publicly [119-120].

We found strong correlations between N/M PIDs and viral titers. We were also able to observe peculiar changes in the signs of the correlations when moved from lung tissues to bronchial ones [40]. We were able to obtain a positive correlation ($r = +0.96$, Figure 6A) especially on the N PID and viral titer ($VT = A * PID_N + B * Time + C$, where $A, B, C =$ coefficients and $VT =$ viral titer). It was, however, very startling when we received a negative correlation ($r = -0.93$, Figure 6B) between PID_M/PID_N and viral titer ($VT = A * PID_M + B * PID_N + C * Time + D$ where $VT =$ viral titer, $A, B, C =$ coefficients and $D = Y$ -intercept) [44]. What is remarkable and puzzling is the change between the positive and negative signs. It is not only reproducing the SDMs but also instructing us on how to use the SDMs. The change in the sign is an indication that the greater presence of particles in the lungs is dependent on the greater N disorder (higher PID_N), whereas the greater viral presence in the bronchi is dependent on lower disorder in N and M PID (lower M PID and N PID). The change in the direction of the slopes (correlations) can be observed in Figure, 6C-D. We will also see that this change in slope (correlation) is completely absent when viral titration is conducted in an animal model, instead of tissues (Figure. 7), as virus particles can easily travel upward via MCC in the case of animal models.

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Figure 6. Multivariate Analysis of M/N Disorder and Viral Titer. **A.** Regression analysis reveals a positive correlation between N PID and the viral titer from human lung tissues and N PID. (Model: $VT = A*(N\ PID) + B*Time + C$ where $VT =$ Viral Titer, $A,B =$ Coefficients , $C =$ Y-Intercept.). **B.** Regression analysis found a negative correlation between viral Titer from human bronchial tissues and M/N PIDs. (Regression model: $VT = A*(M\ PID) + B\ (NPID) + C*Time + D$ where $VT =$ Viral Titer, $A,B,C =$ Coefficients , $D =$ Y-Intercept). **C.** The three dimensional plane with the 95% confidence interval as applied to the regression analysis involving viral titration on the lung tissues. **D.** Three dimensional plane with 95% confidence interval related to the the viral titration using bronchial tissues. As (C) and (D) provide only three dimensional representations (Model: $VT = A*(N\ PID) + B*Time + C$ where $VT =$ Viral Titer, $A,B =$ Coefficients , $C =$ Y-Intercept.), they do not offer a complete picture that can only be found in four dimensions(Regression model: $VT = A*(M\ PID) + B\ (NPID) + C*Time + D$ where $VT =$ Viral Titer, $A,B,C =$ Coefficients , $D =$ Y-Intercept). The analysis is a statistical extension of the experiment of Hui et al. [40,43]. Data pertaining to viral titration and PIDs are from the the experiment of Hui et al and available in Table 2 (which can also be found in previous publications) respectively. A negative slope (correlation) with respect to the N PID-Titer axes can be found in (D), unlike (C).

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Prior to this investigation, we focused on the hard outer shell (low M PID) in resisting the onslaught of mucosal antimicrobial enzymes and on greater N disorder in its ability to assist in providing more efficient viral replication [18-20], but the experiment also showed us that N plays a role in protecting the virion from damage [52,55]. This is something that we had forgotten about, even though we had evidence from the very beginning that harder inner shells do protect the virus from harm in viruses such as EIAV, DENV, and rabies [34-35,55-56,65-67].

We conducted a similar regression study as seen in Figure 7 using the experimental data of Guo et al. [75]. Again, we were able to obtain the titration data from the published paper of Guo et al with the respective N and M PIDs,, which depends on the SARS-CoV-2 variant and pangolin-CoV isolate, obtained from our curated database. As with the data from Hui et al, we did a regression analysis to obtain the correlation coefficients (r) and coefficients of determination (r^2) grouped by the location in the respiratory system the samples were obtained (Figure 7, Total n = 30, $p < 0.01$, $r^2 \sim 0.9$).

Guo et al. used Pang2017 and hamsters in lieu of Omicron and tissue cultures respectively [65]. Therefore, M becomes an unreliable independent variable as there is hardly any difference between the M PID of Pang2017 and non-Omicron SARS-CoV-2. We also expected to see the full effect of MCC since Guo et al. [75] used an animal model, in contrast to the use of tissues by in Hui et al. [78] i.e. the virus particles are more able to move freely between different parts of the respiratory system via MCC. Positive correlations between N PID and viral titer were seen in samples collected from all three areas of the respiratory system as seen in Figure 7, which helps validate SDMs and the results described in the previous sections. Figure 7B affirms a positive slope (correlation) when view with respect to the N PID-Titer plane.

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Figure 7. A) Multivariate analysis of N/M disorder (PID) and viral titer of pangolin-CoV/SARS-CoV-2 in VERO-E6. (Regression: $VT = A * (N \text{ PID}) + B * \text{Time} + C$ where $VT =$ Viral Titer, $A, B =$ Coefficients, $C =$ Intercept). **B.** A three dimensional regression plane and confidence interval with viral titer data from the nasal samples. The results is a statistical extension of the experiment of Guo et al [40,75]. Viral titration data used are from the experiment of Guo et al, whereas PIDs data are available in Table 2 and previous publications. A positive slope (correlation) with respect to the N PID-Titer plane can be seen in (B).

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5.4. Hui et al Experiment: S-Alone Hypothesis Vs. SDMs

The S-alone hypothesis argues that SARS-CoV-1 infects the lower respiratory tract more easily as its S binds more efficiently to the cells in the lower respiratory system. The same argument has been made to account for the lower virulence of Omicron compared to other variant. Hui et al tried to show exactly this. They grew the various variants in bronchi and lung tissues. Their viral titration data show lower viral titers for Omicron in the lungs than bronchial tissues. When we used their viral titration data to do more elaborate statistical analysis to correlate the viral titers to N and M PIDs, our results tell us, however, something different [40]. There are strong correlations between viral titers and N/M PIDs in both bronchial and lung tissues. Not only that, positive and negative correlations were found in the lung and tissues respectively. The results not only reproduce the predictions of SDMs but taught us how to interpret SDMs. The positive correlation between N PID and viral titer in the lungs tells us the greater presence of viral particles is due to the great N disorder (PID), which depends on the variant keeping in mind that the lungs have surfactants, in lieu of mucus. Surfactant has some antimicrobial effects but not the strong array of antimicrobial enzymes present in mucus. That is the reason that there is a strong positive correlation of viral titers in the lung tissues with N PID and small correlation with M PID. The puzzling thing is then: Why is there a negative correlation between viral titer in bronchial tissues and N/M PIDs? The answer has to do with the fact, in contrast to the lung, bronchial tissues, like most upper respiratory tissues, have mucus. A

1126 negatively correlated M PID means that the hard M is protecting virus from
1127 anti-microbial damage. What we did not expect is a correlation with N
1128 disorder. It was then we realized this result is telling us that N also plays a role
1129 in protecting the virion from damage especially when exposed to an onslaught
1130 of antimicrobial enzymes. The results is actually teaching us how to interpret
1131 predictions using SDMs. Indeed, we had previously observed that some
1132 viruses, such as the rabies virus (RABV), with harder inner and outer shells are
1133 more thrive better in harsh environments such as exposure to saliva [65-67]. It
1134 must also be noted that M and N bind to each other in close proximity in the
1135 virion. Further literature search has provided experimental evidence
1136 that M and N together allows greater structural integrity by the non-covalent
1137 binding between the two proteins. This renders support to the computational
1138 results that suggest both M and N protect the virion from damage.
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1140 What our more elaborate statistical analysis is telling us is that the higher viral
1141 titer of Omicron is not due to the difference in the greater presence of viral
1142 particles in the bronchial tissues is not due to the differences in S but due to the
1143 greater ability of the virus in resisting damage from the greater presence of
1144 mucosal antimicrobial enzymes in the bronchial tissues. Omicron's greater
1145 resistance to anti-microbial enzymes arises from its greater hardness in both M
1146 and N (N PID: 44.8%, M PID: 5.4%). The particular Omicron variant used was
1147 BA1, which was the original subvariant that was first detected in South Africa.
1148 While all Omicron variants have lower N PIDs, BA1 has the peculiar
1149 characteristic of even lower M PID (~5.4%) than all other variants or other
1150 Omicron subvariants (~5.9%) [55]. As a result of this and its harder N, it is able
1151 to resist the antimicrobial enzymes in the bronchial tissues and thus there is a
1152 greater presence of viral particles. In the lung tissues, however, there is a lesser
1153 presence of antimicrobial enzymes but because Omicron N PID is much lower
1154 it is unable to replicate as fast as the other variants especially in the lungs. This
1155 is what the more elaborate statistics is detecting, and this result is arguably
1156 more plausible than the one presented by Hui et al [78] as the former shows a
1157 more intricate reason for the results of the latter.
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1159 5.5. *The Role of MCC in Virulence and Infectivity*

1160 Puzzling and seemingly contradictory results is seen in the viral titration
1161 of pangolins as seen in Figure 7 (Guo et al [75]). Unlike the statistical findings
1162 from Hui et al data, the statistical analysis using the data from Guo et al [75]
1163 shows positive correlations for viral titers to N PIDs in both upper and lower
1164 respiratory tracts. This may seem like it is contradictory to the results we have
1165 just discussed, but it is really not. The experiment conducted by Guo et al was
1166 based on live hamster infected with pangolin-CoV. They measured the viral
1167 titers by extracting samples from euthanized hamsters. Hui et al, on the other
1168 hand, relied solely on viruses grown in bronchial and lung tissues respectively.
1169 Therefore, we should expect the full effects of MCC in experiment of Guo et al,
1170 but only limited MCC effect in the experiment of Hui et al. Because the viral
1171 particles produced all over the respiratory system including the lower
1172 respiratory system will move upward towards the nasal region for expulsion.
1173 That is exactly what the statistical result in Figure 7, unlike Figure 6, is telling
1174 us. The results of Figures 6-7 do cast doubt on the hypothesis that SARS-CoV-1
1175 is less infectious but more virulent is caused by the ability its S to bind more
1176 easily to the ACE-2 cells in the lower respiratory tracts because MCC entails
1177 that much of the particles produced even in lower respiratory tracts to be
1178 transported upwards to the nasal region to be expelled from the body. The
1179 same argument has been made for the more virulent SARS-CoV-2 variants. It
1180 seems that a more plausible scenario is that the virus replicates about the same
1181 amount throughout the respiratory system. The more virulence strain or
1182 variant with higher N PID replicates in larger quantities throughout the
1183 respiratory system especially in the lungs but whether much of the particles is
1184 expelled from the body depends if the virus is resistant to the onslaught of
1185 mucosal and salivary antimicrobial enzymes via a harder M.
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1187 5.6. *SDMs Account for MCC: Virulence Vs. Infectivity*

1188 One problem with the "S-Alone" hypothesis involving SARS-CoV-1/2 virulence
1189 and infectivity is that it is oblivious of current physiological knowledge, namely MCC.
1190 Even if SARS-CoV-1 does bind more efficiently to the lower respiratory tract
1191 compared to upper respiratory tract and thereby making SARS-CoV-1 less infectious

1192 but more virulent, MCC entails that the viral particles will move upward towards the
1193 nasal region to be expunged. This is, of course, assuming that the viral particles will
1194 survive the onslaught of anti-microbial enzymes during the transportation by mucus-
1195 covered ciliary cells. The MCC factor has to be taken into account if we attempt to
1196 demonstrate the difference in virulence and infectivity between Omicron and non-
1197 Omicron variants. Because MCC is an important principle in physiology, MCC must
1198 therefore be essential in explaining the mechanisms for virulence and infectivity
1199 manifestations. SDMs, unlike the S-alone hypothesis, able to account for MCC and
1200 MCC can help explain the link between infectivity and virulence via SDMs. MCC and
1201 SDMs therefore compliment each other to account for the differences in infectivity and
1202 virulence manifestations of SARS-CoV-1/2 and SARS-CoV-2 variants.
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5.7. *The HCoV-NL63 Enigma*

1205 The above sections do not show that S does not play any role in infectivity
1206 and virulence but, rather, that S does not play the roles in infectivity and
1207 virulence in many of the ways we think it does. Its roles should be seen in the
1208 broader context alongside other proteins such as N and M. To understand it
1209 further we turn our attention to another human CoV. The only other known
1210 human CoV (HCoV), other than SARS-CoV-1/2, that binds to ACE-2 is NL63 [121-
1211 126]. HCoV-NL30 usually manifests itself as a mild cold even though it known to be
1212 capable of infecting both the lower and upper respiratory tracts. NL63 and SARS-CoV-
1213 1/2 are not closely related as they are alphacoronavirus and betacoronavirus respectively
1214 [126]. It can be argued that NL63 is somewhat less infectious than SARS-CoV-2
1215 since the former usually infects only children and immunocompromised
1216 individuals such as the elderly, unlike the latter.
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1218 NL63 has no FCS-recognition site even if a FCS sequence has been detected at S2
1219 [123-124]. While cleavage is seen at the Golgi apparatus of cells infected by SARS-
1220 CoV-2, it is not seen in NL63 infection. Keeping in mind that SARS-CoV-1 does not
1221 have FCS, unlike SARS-CoV-2 [101-103], the absence of an FCS recognition site
1222 presents an intriguing enigma. If NL63 and SARS-CoV1 have no FCS-recognition
1223 site, why is NL63 obviously less infectious than SARS-CoV-1? Conversely, if SARS-
1224 CoV-2 has an FCS-recognition site, unlike NL63 and SARS-CoV-1, why does SARS-
1225 CoV-2 has an infectivity that is comparable to NL63, when compared to SARS-CoV-1,
1226 given the fact that both COVID-19 and NL63, not SARS-CoV-1, are endemic? We
1227 know that SARS-CoV-1 has limited infectivity as there was only 8,422 known cases of
1228 infection and it is now extinct, whereas COVID-19 and NL63 is endemic even to this
1229 day [3,12126]. All these seem to contradict the idea that the presence of FCS is
1230 responsible for higher infectivity [102-103]. As for pathogenesis, why are SARS-CoV-
1231 2 and NL63 much less virulent than SARS-CoV-1 when SARS-CoV-2 is the only virus
1232 of the three that has FCS-recognition site, given that the presence of FCS is associated
1233 with greater pathogenesis?
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1235 Likewise, the relationship between S-ACE-2 affinity and pathogenesis or infectivity
1236 can cast much confusion especially when NL63 is taken in to consideration. As we have
1237 seen the affinity of SARS-CoV-2 S to human ACE-2 is much higher than that of
1238 SARS-CoV-1. Many scientists have postulated that this discrepancy is responsible for
1239 SARS-CoV-2 higher infectivity especially among humans [9-11]. This postulation is,
1240 however, unreplicable when it has been shown that NL63 S affinity for ACE-2 is
1241 less than that of SARS-CoV-1 [126]. How could this be possible when it NL63 is
1242 obviously much more infectious than SARS-CoV-1 for the reasons already mentioned?
1243 All these questions form a conundrum that is difficult to be explained by S alone and is
1244 more effectively explained when the different roles of S, N and M are taken into
1245 consideration.
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1248 This virus is, however, also enigmatic for SDMs as its N disorder is very close to that
1249 of SARS-CoV-1 (N PIDs: 49.8% vs 50.2%) but NL63 is, of course, not as virulent.
1250 Does that mean that SDMs are wrong? If we look closely, we will find that this is not
1251 necessarily true. SDMs usually work better when the viruses that are compared are
1252 closely related. NL63 is not closely related to SARS-CoV-1/2 as a result the proteins in
1253 general are not similar between the two. Because of the differences in proteins
1254 especially those other than the shell proteins, other factors can come into play such as
1255 differences in toxicities of other proteins. This is a limitation of SDMs.

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Nevertheless, in this case, comparison using SDMs is possible in this case. While the NL63 N PID is higher than SARS-CoV-2 but comparable to SARS-CoV-1, the M disorder tells a different story. It is higher much higher than that of SARS-CoV-1/2 (NL63 M PID: ~11%, SARS-CoV-2 M PID: 5.8-54.%, SARS-CoV-1 M PID: ~9%). If you apply what is already known about SDMs, the relatively soft NL63 M and N means that even though relatively much higher viral particles are produced even in the lower respiratory tract, the particles are easily damaged by the mucosal antimicrobial enzymes the moment they are produced. It is for this reason that NL63 is usually not dangerous. If we scrutinize the clinical data more carefully, however, we see that NL63 is capable of infecting both the upper and lower respiratory tracts [121-122] and that the people it infects in this manner are mainly children and immunocompromised adults such as elderly. These clinical manifestations may be the result of the ability to replicate in larger quantities in all areas of the respiratory system if unchecked by the immune system including the anti-microbial enzymes in the mucus. SDMs also suggest that despite its greater vulnerability to damage by mucosal antimicrobial enzymes, some particles are able to reach the nasal region to be shed because greater quantities are produced as a result of a more disordered N. The fact that children and immunocompromised adults are more easily infected could place further support to the idea that only limited quantities of viral particles are shed. Children often play in close contact with each other especially at preschools.

5.8. *The Protective Roles of Outer and Inner Shells*

We have seen how both the outer (M) and inner (N) shells play roles in protecting SARS-CoV-2 from antimicrobial enzymes in the mucus and saliva. Apparently, this is not the only virus that have shown such properties. There are several papers that show that viruses that are exposed to saliva usually have hard outer shells and often have also hard inner shells. Examples of such viruses are EIAV, rabies virus and Zika virus [4,34-35,66-67]. EIAV is transmitted between horses via a horsefly that sucks blood of an infected horse that is store in the insect's mouthpiece containing its saliva before it sucks the blood of a new host, which is thereby infected. The rabies virus resides near the salivary gland of the host and is therefore exposed to saliva. Similarly, ZIKV is exposed to saliva as it is held in the mouth of a Aedes mosquito upon feeding on the blood of an infected host. These, however, do not necessarily mean that all viruses have inner shell hardness even all viruses exposed to saliva usually have hard outer shells. This is the case in the flavivirus family, in which the viruses are usually insect-borne and have hard outer M but a few such as ZIKV have also harder capsid.

5.9. *The Functions of M and N*

A great way to gain more insights into the structure, nature and functions of viral proteins such as N and M is by inspecting the SARS-CoV-2 using microscopy especially electron microscopy (EM) [127-128]. Inspections of the SARS-CoV-2 using powerful EM have revealed the reasons that M and N are the most abundant proteins in the virion and cell respectively. M spans the entire membrane than enclose the entire virion whereas N encases the RNA genome [127-128]. The structural arrangement itself suggests protective roles of the two proteins. M binds strongly to both S and N. The affinities for S and N allows M and N to play important roles in assembly and budding of viral particles [107]. Because of the strong affinity between M and N, greater flexibility in N provides for more efficient recognition between N and M [16,30-32]. This is one of the reasons that greater N disorder allows faster and effective viral replication.

There is yet another property of M and N that has been observed using EM. This involves the nature of of M and N binding. Powerful EM was able to observe that the C-terminus of M binds to N via an ionic interaction [129] and in the absence of this interaction, the entire virion collapses under harsh conditions such high salt or PH. This important observation renders support to the suggestion that M and N play roles in protecting the virion. While M protects the entire virion, N is likely to protect

1317 specifically the genomic RNA by the fact that N encases the RNA and thus the is
1318 strong affinities between the two entities [106-109]. The N affinity to the viral RNA
1319 has given N many important roles especially those pertaining to viral replication. This
1320 includes assembly and RNA transcription [107-109,129-131]. Because of its important
1321 multiple roles in replication and the life-cycle of the virus, we are able to see how N
1322 disorder can easily affect virulence and infectivity along with M disorder as greater N
1323 disorder promotes easier protein-protein/RNA/lipid/carbohydrate recognition [16,30-
1324 33,68].

1325
1326 We have tried to show that SDMs is highly reproducible and can account for
1327 many of the properties and manifestation of SARS-CoV-2 related viruses and COVID-
1328 19. Such reproducibilities should not be surprising as M and N are the most abundant
1329 proteins in the virion and cell respectively and they play major roles in the life cycle of
1330 the virus especially with regard to its replication [106-109]. Nevertheless, we need to
1331 keep in mind that M and N are, of course, not the only viral proteins in CoVs. While
1332 they play major roles in the replication of the virus, other proteins also play roles. For
1333 instance, N binds to NSP2 before transcription of viral RNA takes place [129]. Since it
1334 involves other proteins, we should therefore expect limitations and potentials in N and
1335 M just as we have seen this in S. One such example is the use of Virulence-Inner SDM
1336 to compare distant viruses within a family. This is the case when the viruses proteins
1337 are essentially very different in sequences and use different receptors. Other examples
1338 of the limitation of SDMs can be detected in the results certain animal and viral
1339 titration studies. Discussion in further details can be seen in the next subsection.

1342 1343 1344 *5.10. A More Accurate Understanding of S Comes with the Study of Other Proteins*

1345 The above sections do not show that S does not play any role in infectivity
1346 and virulence but, rather, that S does not play the roles in infectivity and
1347 virulence that many scientists have envisaged. To be able to gain a more
1348 accurate understanding the real role of S, a better understanding of the role of
1349 other viral proteins, especially the more abundant major proteins, is necessary.

1350 We have presented evidence to show that S is not able to account for the
1351 differences in virulence and infectivity between SARS-CoV-1 and SARS-CoV-2.
1352 We have also seen that the viral titers of the two viruses are different with
1353 higher titer, implying higher virulence in the case of SARS-CoV-1. While the
1354 presence and absence of FCS in SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV-1 respectively
1355 could explain the greater virulence of SARS-CoV-1, it does not explain the
1356 greater virulence of the latter. The SDMs using N and M provide a
1357 comprehensive and coherent explanation that is more reproducible. The SDMs
1358 are also able to explain the differences among COVID-19 viruses, even if they
1359 are more complex. Much of the problem lies in the fact that many of the viruses
1360 have yet to be observed to spread to the human population, and their actual
1361 pathogenicity and infectivity among humans cannot be accurately determined.
1362 For these, we have to rely on animal models, the use of which is tricky and
1363 requires extrapolation. Wrong inferences based on incorrect extrapolations and
1364 assumptions can easily be made, as we have seen in the disastrous pre-clinical
1365 studies of thalidomide using mice, rats and rabbits [133].

1366
1367
1368 In the case of COVID-19, it was believed that the FCS is responsible for
1369 infectiousness and virulence based on an animal model, in which infected and
1370 uninfected ferrets were caged together. One group had a few ferrets infected
1371 with a wild-type SARS-CoV-2 (WT), whereas the other had a few that were
1372 infected with a mutated strain without FCS. The result was that the WT did
1373 infect some of the uninfected ferrets, whereas those infected with FCS-mutant
1374 did not infect others [112]. Based on this experiment, it is easy to come to
1375 conclusion that FCS is responsible for high transmissibility. A picture that
1376 contradicts this conclusion was obtained when similar experiments were
1377 performed using pangolin-CoVs and Omicron.

1378
1379 In various independent laboratories, uninfected Syrian hamsters were
1380 easily infected by those infected with pangolin-CoVs (Pang2017 and Pang2019)

1381 when caged together by contact, though not as easily as via aerosol [75-76,81].
1382 Similar experiments using Omicron yielded comparable results [76-77,114-115].
1383 Furthermore, it was seen that Wuhan-Hu-1 is more easily spread via aerosol,
1384 whereas pangolin-CoVs and, to some extent, Omicron were not, even though
1385 the latter have been shown to spread easily clinically. Keeping in mind that
1386 pangolin-CoVs don't have FCS but Omicron does, these experiments highlight
1387 that the issue is more complex than it seems, and it is easy to come to the
1388 wrong conclusion without a more complete picture. Adding to the confusion,
1389 why does Pang2019 show as much virulence as Wuhan-Hu-1 that is not seen in
1390 Pang2017 and Omicron?
1391

1392 A more complete and reproducible answer can be found if the analysis
1393 takes the various roles of N, M, and S into consideration. It is obvious that S
1394 does play some role in the infectivity of the virus, but it is a mistake to assume
1395 that this role is as overreaching as suggested by some. SDMs explain that all
1396 thus far know variants are highly infectious as COVID-19 patients shed large
1397 quantities of the virus because its hard outer shell M helps prevent virion
1398 disintegration caused by salivary and mucosal enzymes before being expelled
1399 by the body. While the abnormally hard M ensures a certain high level of
1400 spread, higher N PID (ie. Higher levels of N disorder) leads to greater levels of
1401 viral replication and viral load (the mechanism has been explained in
1402 subsection 5.9), especially in vital organs such as the lungs, that could increase
1403 the virulence of the virus and the amount of viral particles expunged from the
1404 body, even if the quantity of virus shedding is already high. This is exactly the
1405 case with Wuhan-Hu-1 and Omicron. Omicron has a relatively low N Disorder
1406 (PID ~43%) and is therefore milder than the other variants, but it is also
1407 infectious as it has also low M PIDs (~5.4-5.9). Wuhan-Hu-1, on the other hand,
1408 is both highly infectious and more virulent as its M and N PIDs are low and
1409 relatively high, respectively. The aforementioned animal model suggests that
1410 Wuhan-Hu-1 is relatively more infectious than Omicron. Since both SDMs and
1411 clinical studies suggest high infectiousness in the two viruses, the experiment
1412 can only be consistent with SDMs and clinical studies if the infectiousness of
1413 the two viruses are only relative in differences [71-73,114-115]. We have to be
1414 careful when using animal models since extrapolation is necessary when we
1415 attempt to link the results to human infections [132].
1416

1417 Furthermore, human infectivity tells only part of the story in the evolution of SARS-
1418 CoV-2 and its ancestral strain. We must also keep in mind the infectivity of the SARS-
1419 CoV-2 and its relatives in different animal hosts. Furthermore, we must pay attention to
1420 data pertaining to virulence including viral titration and cell damage. As virulence can
1421 be linked to infectivity using the SDMs and MCC as shown in 5.4-5.6, these factors
1422 are important when it comes to interpretation of the results of animal models involving
1423 infectivity. We will also see in the next section that the best understanding of the
1424 results comes when we use our knowledge of S, N and M in tandem.
1425

1426 *5.11. Biological Implications of a More Rigid M*

1427 We have seen in Figure 2 that all SARS-CoV-2 related viruses have an extraordinarily
1428 hard outer, M. Nearly all CoVs have PIDs of above 8. The exceptions are CoVs
1429 associated with burrowing animals. CoVs closely related to SARS-CoV-2 have M PIDs
1430 between 4% through 6.3% (Table 2, Supplementary Table). The differences between
1431 burrowing and non-burrowing seem small even if statistically significant. A clearer
1432 understanding comes, however, if we consider the functions and virion physiology
1433 related to M. M is the most abundant viral protein that spans the entire virion.
1434 Therefore, even with a few mutations that lowers the disorder of M, the rigidity of the
1435 SARS-CoV-2 membrane is likely be strengthened greatly by the sheer abundance of
1436 M. This is especially so when the virus is in its native state when M plays the essential
1437 role of protecting the virion from external insults.
1438

1439 A question that arises is: If SARS-CoV-2 M is more rigid, how is it able to perform its
1440 other functions that requires conformational changes such as viral entry and protein
1441 assembly. If we look at Table 2, we see that the minimum M PID seen in all CoVs is
1442 around 4%. Obviously, this is the minimum level of disorder that is needed for M to
1443 have just enough flexibility in order to perform its other roles that require
1444 conformational change. A M PID of 0% theoretically means that the protein is has no
1445

1446 room for conformation changes. Therefore, an M PID of 0 % means that the virus is
1447 not functional. The data in Table 2 and Figure 2 seem to reinforce this idea by the
1448 existence of the 4% minimum cutoff point. While a lower M PID offers greater
1449 protection to the virus in its native state, it could also imply that M could have less
1450 efficiency in undergoing conformational changes. We don't, however, know how much
1451 impact this has on the efficiency of conformational changes that are necessary for
1452 processes such as viral entry and protein assembly. Extrapolating from the efficiency of
1453 SARS-CoV-2 (M PID ~ 6.3%) in replication, it is likely not that much, but, again, this
1454 is just an extrapolation that has to be confirmed by experimental results.

1457 **5.12.** *A Comparative Analysis of SARS-CoV-2, Pangolin-CoVs, and Laotian Bat- CoV* 1458 *Experiments Using S, N, and M*

1459
1460 A more comprehensive analysis can be accomplished when examining M,
1461 N, and S in experimental data for SARS-CoV-2, bat-CoVs, and pangolin-CoVs.
1462 We have seen that all COVID-19-related viruses are potentially infectious
1463 because of their abnormally hard M. We have also seen that Pang2019,
1464 BANAL: (Laotian bat-CoV) and Wuhan-Hu-1 are all potentially virulent
1465 because of their high N PIDs (~48%), whereas Pang2017 and Omicron are
1466 attenuated as a result of their relatively low N PIDs (~44%). These have been
1467 largely reproduced. Cells infected with Pang2017 or Omicron have signs of
1468 lower viral growth and cytopathic effects [55,74]. Similarly, animal models
1469 have shown less severity. In contrast, however, viral titers of cells infected by
1470 Pang2019 [80-82] and Wuhan-Hu-1 [75,79] are higher than those infected by
1471 Pang2017 or Omicron [55,74-76], just as predicted by the SDMs. In contrast,
1472 mice were observed to be severely sickened by Pang2019 [81-82]. We need to
1473 keep in mind that this trend is true despite the fact that FCS is found only in
1474 SARS-CoV-2 including Omicron. Therefore, the stark differences in the results
1475 of the various experiments can only be accounted for when the roles of N and
1476 M are considered.

1478 1479 **5.13.** *Evidence of the Potentials and Limitations of S: Viral Entry and Replication*

1480
1481
1482 The data for the Laotian bat-CoVs present an enigma [50-51]. It was
1483 shown that BANAL S binds to ACE2 in a different manner from SARS-CoV-2
1484 even as the BANAL viruses bind efficiently to human cells. Ironically, even
1485 though the N PID of BANAL is close to those of Wuhan-Hu-1 and Pang2019,
1486 no severe disease was detected in mice infected by BANAL-236. This seemed
1487 inconsistent with what SDMs predicted until the data were studied very
1488 carefully. If we inspect the viral titration data, we can see that the viral titers in
1489 VERO-E6 cells is high and comparable to Wuhan-Hu-1, but this is not the case
1490 in CALU-3 cells, where the difference is larger; it should also be kept in mind
1491 that a VERO-E6 cell is of kidney origin, whereas CALU cells are respiratory.
1492 This implies that BANAL-236 is more adapted to kidney cells than respiratory
1493 ones presumably because of its S structure. We also need to keep in mind that
1494 it has been observed that the Laotian bat-CoV S binds to ACE-2 in a different
1495 manner [51].

1496 While this serves as evidence that S does play a role in infectivity, it does
1497 not show that SDM results are wrong or not reproducible. Instead, it points to
1498 the correct way that SDMs should be interpreted. Firstly, the experimental data
1499 remind us that SDMs predict *potential* virulence, not necessarily actual
1500 virulence, and this potential virulence arises from the high viral load in at least
1501 one organ, which is populated with cells that the virus can enter more easily. A
1502 second lesson to be learned from the data is that SDMs predict virulence in
1503 general, not just humans, since N PID correlates best with highest viral titers
1504 among various cell types [55,74-79], and high viral load is associated with
1505 organ failures. While human COVID-19 fatality is mainly associated with
1506 pulmonary (lung) failures, this may not be necessarily so for other animals.
1507 Therefore, SDMs are predicting potential virulence in general, not just in
1508 humans.

1510
1511 If there is evidence that S does play some role in infectivity and virulence
1512 via viral load, the question then becomes: how easily does S adapt to bind
1513 more efficiently? It would seem that greater S fitness may be more easily
1514 acquired than many believe. Experiments have shown that COVID-19 viruses
1515 acquire greater ability to infect the lungs after passing to humanized mice
1516 several times [133-136]. Furthermore, a closer comparison of the two may
1517 provide clues. Given the fact that both BANAL-236 and Pang2019 have high N
1518 PIDs, why has Pang2019 been shown to be virulent to humanized mice, unlike
1519 BANAL-236? Evidently, Pang2019 S is more adapted than BANAL-236. To
1520 understand how this is the case, we need to look at the evolutionary
1521 differences between the two viruses. If we look at Figure 5B, which is a
1522 phylogenetic tree using M, we see that Pang2019 is much more closely related
1523 to SARS-CoV-2 than BANAL-236. This implies that Pang2019 was exposed to a
1524 similar range of hosts as Wuhan-Hu-1. What is also remarkable is that both
1525 BANAL-236 and Pangolin-CoVs, unlike SARS-CoV-2, do not have FCS. It is
1526 likely that Pang2019 split off from SARS-CoV-2 to infect mainly pangolins, and
1527 as a result lost its FCS while still maintaining much of the rest of its S structure.
1528 This may also have implications for Peacock et al.'s FCS-mutant experiment
1529 [113] It is possible that FCS-deficient S compensates for its deficit by binding to
1530 ACE-2 in a different way over the long run as in the case of Pang2019, and, as
1531 we will see, it is easy for S to quickly adapt to the ACE-2 of a particular species
1532 or cell type in a laboratory.

1533
1534 It is evident that S has to be at least sufficiently adapted to ACE-2 in order
1535 to even be infectious, but in order for SARS-CoV-2 to have any sustained
1536 infectivity or virulence, other factors must also come in crucial play, especially
1537 the roles of M and N, as seen in the experimental and clinical evidence
1538 pertaining to SARS-CoV-1/2. The question then becomes: how difficult it is for
1539 S to gain sufficient adaptation to respiratory cells? The earlier section argues
1540 that it may not be that difficult. Several studies have shown that COVID-19
1541 viruses can easily acquire adaptability to human respiratory cells in the
1542 laboratory very quickly [133-136]. Acquiring abnormally hard M that provides
1543 for potentially high infectivity, on the other hand, may not be that easy. It is
1544 easy to find CoVs that efficiently bind to S of respiratory cells [101,109,118] or
1545 have FCS [101,109,118] or that S easily adapts [108,131-132], but it is difficult to
1546 find CoVs with the abnormally hard M, as most CoVs are not intimately
1547 associated with a burrowing animal unlike COVID-19 related viruses [4,16-
1548 20,53-56] .

1549 1550 **5.14. Greater Model Reproducibility and Reliability Come When More Proteins are** 1551 **Considered**

1552
1553 The greater reliability and reproducibility of SDMs, in large part, arise
1554 from the fact that they take into account the disorder of two major proteins, M
1555 and N, which are most abundant in the virion and infected cell respectively. In
1556 fact, SDMs become unreliable if M or N is omitted from consideration. SDMs
1557 are reliable and reproducible in most cases except in certain occasions when
1558 the role of S has to be taken into serious consideration as we have seen in the
1559 case of the Laotian bat-CoVs. For this reason, we cannot dismiss S or any other
1560 proteins as unimportant. In fact, as we have shown, SDMs become even more
1561 reliable and reproducible when S (or other protein) is taken into consideration.
1562 This trend is consistent with what we know about the biology of viral
1563 replication. Viral replication involves multiple proteins even if there are
1564 proteins that play more major roles than others.

1565 1566 1567 **5.15. Limitations and Potentials of N, M and SDMs**

1568 We have already touched on the limitation of SDMs. We have seen that it
1569 cannot account some of the experimental results conducted using BANAL
1570 (Laotian bat-CoVs). They are, for example, unable to account for the differences
1571 in the the viral titrations of BANAL-236 and SARS-CoV-2 on different cell
1572 types (e.g. CALU, COCA, Vero-E6) [51-52,77]. The significance of the
1573 differences is, however, needs further investigation as other researchers have
1574 shown that SARS-CoV-2 becomes more efficient in replication as several
1575 passages are made in each cell type. Nevertheless, this points to the role of S,

1576 which is a limitation of the SDMs. Currently, SDMs involves on the viral shell
1577 proteins, which, in the case of CoVs, are the N and M. Given that SARS-CoV-2
1578 has 29 viral proteins and many of them are involved in the replication process
1579 [106-109], there will be limitation if only one or two proteins are used to study
1580 infectivity, virulence or long COVID. This is, of course, the case in SDMs,
1581 which currently use only M and N. In fact, as already mentioned, without
1582 either M or N, SDMs would be of limited reproducibility and reliability and
1583 would have much difficulty explaining the underlying cause of infectivity and
1584 virulence.

1585
1586 Ironically, the question is then: How could M and N account for infectivity and
1587 virulence with even a decent level of reproducibility and reliability when the
1588 limitation of using only two proteins is considered? The answer could lie in
1589 two factors. The important roles of M and N, as seen above, are likely to be
1590 partly responsible. Secondly, a hint of an overwhelming importance of M and
1591 N can be seen by the massive abundance of the proteins, not seen in other
1592 COVID-19 viral proteins. This could also reinforce the idea that the two
1593 proteins are playing greater major roles in the functioning of the virus. While
1594 the focus of this review paper is on SDMs, N and M, it is not intended to
1595 dismiss the importance of S or any other viral protein. This review, however,
1596 attempts to underscore the importance of M and N in infectivity and virulence
1597 as exemplified by the exercise seen in Figures 6-7. The results seen in Figures 6-
1598 7 do not invalidate the role of S, as Hui et al attempted to demonstrate but,
1599 rather, suggest that the currently understudied roles of M and N could even
1600 overshadow that of S with respect to infectivity, virulence and, potentially,
1601 long COVID. Of course, SDMs would become more reproducible and reliable
1602 if more viral proteins such as S and NSP7 are considered in the models, but,
1603 currently, SDMs have not reach the stage where the roles of more proteins can
1604 be incorporated.

1609 6. Pangolin Footprints and Long COVID

1611 6.1. The Long COVID Enigma and Pangolin Footprints

1612 One unusual characteristic that is often found among some COVID-19
1613 patients is long COVID, which is when symptoms persist for weeks, months, or
1614 even years after the initial infection [57-58,110-111]. While the cause of long
1615 COVID remains largely a mystery, SDMs offer the most logical and plausible
1616 explanation yet. We have seen that all COVID-19 related viruses have
1617 extraordinarily hard outer shell (M) that is not found in any CoVs except those
1618 associated with burrowing animals. We have also seen how SDMs explain that
1619 the hard M allows for greater infectiousness of COVID-19, by providing more
1620 resistance to mucosal and salivary antimicrobial enzymes, often without
1621 greater virulence that is associated with greater N disorder [18-20,52,55-56].
1622 Just as a hard M provides resistance to antimicrobial enzymes, it will almost
1623 certainly also provide resistance to other destructive mechanisms offered by
1624 other aspects of the host immune system. This is possible as clinical studies
1625 have shown that large amounts of the virus tend to remain in the body even
1626 after months [110-111]. We will further explore this link by a further
1627 examination of the various known aspects of immunology related to this
1628 matter as seen in the following subsections.

1631 6.2. Hard M Resistance to Virolysis by Macrophages and Complement System

1632 In order to further examine the role of an abnormally hard M in long
1633 COVID, we need to look more closely at how the immune system gets rid of
1634 invading foreign particles, especially viruses. Our knowledge of immunology
1635 helps us to focus our attention on proteins produced by the complement
1636 system and lysosome [135-142]. These enzymes are experimentally shown to
1637 damage viruses and viral membranes.
1638

1639 Complement proteins are produced mainly by hepatocytes in the liver,
1640 even though they are secreted by monocytes, macrophages, and epithelial cells
1641 in the intestines. There are, at least, 30 types of complement proteins [139]. B
1642 and T cells, along with antibodies, can alert the complement system in the
1643 presence of a foreign matter such as bacteria or virus. Complementary proteins
1644 assemble and bind to a protein at the targeted membrane, and the protein
1645 complex punches holes in the membrane. Apoptosis occurs in the case of
1646 bacteria or infected cells, whereas, in the case of a virus, this is referred to as
1647 virolysis. It is at this point in COVID-19 and long COVID that the hard M may
1648 make it difficult for the complement system to do its job, as the proteins are
1649 likely unable to penetrate the membrane since M spans the entire membrane
1650 that covers the virion.
1651
1652

1653 *6.3. Resistance to Virolysis Within a Macrophage May Provide the Virus a Place to* 1654 *Dwell: Possible Reservoir*

1655
1656 A second way that the immune system attempts to get rid of pathogens is
1657 to expose them to digestive enzymes [130-131,140]. The macrophage will first
1658 engulf the microbe or microbial protein, and upon phagocytosis, the immune
1659 system will attempt to digest the particle via lysosomes [138-141]. The problem
1660 with this strategy, however, is that many pathogens are somehow resistant to
1661 the exposure of digestive enzymes and end up living in the macrophages
1662 themselves [140-141]. An ongoing enigma pertaining to long COVID involves
1663 the possibility of a reservoir that harbors the virus long after the initial
1664 infection of the patient and where the source actually is, since a hard outer
1665 shell could prevent the macrophage from destroying the virus and the virus
1666 ends up living in the macrophage. The observation of an abnormally hard M,
1667 along with our knowledge of immunology, suggests that the first place to look
1668 at is none other than the macrophage itself, and current research supports this.
1669 Huot et al. [144] found the presence of SARS-CoV-2 in the lungs of patients
1670 with symptoms of long COVID, whereas several other research groups have
1671 found presence in organs and tissues throughout the body [110-111], which is
1672 consistent with the fact that macrophages can be found in nearly all organs in
1673 the body [139].
1674

1675 The nature of SARS-CoV-2 should not be confused with that of other
1676 viruses such as HIV and HSV. The fact that SARS-CoV-2 has among the
1677 hardest outer shell, not just among CoVs but also among all viruses, is a tell-
1678 tale sign that the virus is of a different nature from other viruses such as HSV
1679 and HIV-2 that are known to hide in places such as the brain only to show up
1680 later [109]. HIV and HSV-2 have one of the most disordered outer shells
1681 among viruses, unlike SARS-CoV-2. Their highly disordered outer shells help
1682 them penetrate and hide in organs, as greater disorder allows for more efficient
1683 protein-protein binding. SARS-CoV-2, on the other hand, has one of the
1684 hardest outer shells. If it does not have the benefit of a disordered outer shell,
1685 how does it hide? The answer has to lie in the mechanism of phagocytosis
1686 described above. There is research showing that inflammatory responses may
1687 be responsible for long COVID. A hard M and inflammatory responses such as
1688 those caused by cytokines are not mutually exclusive [142-144]. Because of the
1689 extraordinarily hardness of M, it provides for a unique way for SARS-CoV-2 to hide in
1690 macrophages only to appear whenever the opportunity arises. Whenever the virus
1691 keeps reappearing, the immune system could respond in such a way that could result
1692 also in inflammation caused by cytokines.
1693

1694 *6.4. Granuzymes: A Suspected Mechanism of M Resistance*

1695 While the exposure of destructive enzymes has been shown to act against
1696 viruses in the complement system and macrophages, there are also other
1697 destructive enzymes available in the immune system. These involve a family of
1698 enzymes known as granuzymes. Upon entry of the virus, the immune system
1699 will initiate a variety of defensive actions that include Cytotoxic T-Cells and
1700 Natural Killer (NK) cells, which secrete substances that could potentially
1701 damage viral particles [136-139]. These cells secrete granuzymes in response to
1702 a foreign invader. One of the granuzymes is perforin, which binds to plasma
1703 membranes and punches holes that allows other granuzymes to enter to cause
1704 further damage to the bacterium or infected cell [145]. While current

1705 experimental evidence has shown this to occur in membranes of bacteria and
1706 infected cells, there is currently no evidence that it damages viral membranes.
1707 Nevertheless, given the known biochemical capabilities of perforin , it can be
1708 construed that perforin can potentially damage virion in the same manner,
1709 since most animal viruses including SARS-CoV-2 have a protective outer
1710 membrane layer to protect themselves. In any case, perforin causes lysis in
1711 infected cells, and thereby allows the virus particles to be exposed to the
1712 complement system and macrophages. It is also known that, while T-Cells and
1713 NK cells secrete perforin, macrophages secrete perforin-2 (PFN2), which is
1714 similar to perforin, but it remains unclear if PFN2 affect viral membranes
1715 directly [144-145].

1716 6.5. Uniqueness of COVID-19 Strategy of Immune Evasion in Long COVID

1719 There are many mysteries involving long COVID that physicians and
1720 scientists are still struggling to solve so that we can come up better treatments.
1721 How does SARS-CoV-2 induce long COVID? What are the mechanisms? Is
1722 there a reservoir? If so, where is it? As we have seen, SDMs offer specific
1723 answers to these questions. While N disorder modulates the amount of virus
1724 replicated, especially in vital organs, the unusually hard M provides resistance
1725 to antimicrobial enzymes. Therefore, the immune evasion strategy used by
1726 SARS-CoV-2 is drastically different from that of viruses such as HIV, HSV, and
1727 HCV [4,16-20,65-67], which have high disorder in the outer shell that allows
1728 such viruses to hide in organs. Not only has no such high disorder been
1729 detected in SARS-CoV-2, the virus has one of the hardest outer shell among
1730 viruses, not just CoVs. That is why the macrophages offer the virus the
1731 opportunity to dwell and hide in them. Indeed, one laboratory showed the
1732 presence of the virus in the lung alveolar macrophages of patients who tested
1733 negative for the virus in the upper respiratory system [143]. What is even more
1734 puzzling is that several other laboratories have observed the presence of the
1735 virus in many organs of long COVID patients [111-112]. This raises the
1736 question, where is the reservoir? Again, if macrophages are the reservoir, the
1737 virus will be present in these various organs since macrophages are found in
1738 nearly every organ in the body.

1740 6.6. Long COVID, long SARS and S

1741 Long COVID has been linked to the activation of the immune system, via,
1742 particularly, interferons (IFN- γ) and natural killer T-cells (NK cells), that
1743 results in inflammation [142,144]. Many scientists point to S as the main
1744 underlying cause of the activation. While this postulation is very interesting
1745 and plausible, it raises more questions than it answers. For instance, it doesn't
1746 tell us the reason why some people get long COVID, whereas, others don't. It
1747 doesn't tell us if long COVID arises from a reservoir and, if so, what is the
1748 source of the reservoir i.e. the hiding place of the virus. We also need to
1749 remember that SARS-CoV-1 has a CoV S protein too. Because the two viruses
1750 are relatively closely related (80%), it is likely the S of both viruses are
1751 functionally similar including their ability to activate the immune system in
1752 similar ways. A conundrum is , however, seen when upon an examination of
1753 the differences between long COVID and long SARS. One stark difference is
1754 the fact that long SARS was usually associated with severe manifestation of the
1755 disease, whereas long COVID could come even with mild symptoms [64]. How
1756 could there be such a disparity if the S proteins of the two viruses are likely to
1757 be structurally similar and when it has been shown that S activates the immune
1758 system [142,144], which is likely to cause long COVID. SDMs offers a novel
1759 explanation. SDMs have observed that SARS-CoV-2 has a much harder M than
1760 that of SARS-CoV-1 as a result the virus is able to resist the immune enzymes
1761 and hide in the macrophage in the case of COVID. We are, therefore, likely to
1762 get a better picture when we consider the roles of M. N and S keeping in mind
1763 that N also plays a role as greater N disorder could allow greater production of
1764 viral particles even in the event of long COVID.

1767 7. Summary and Conclusion

1768
1769 7.1. *Reproducibility and Reliability of SDMs: Experimental and Clinical Evidence*

1770
1771 Some of the clinical and experimental evidence of the reproducibility and
1772 reliability are as follows:

1773
1774
1775 .i) The extraordinary hardiness of SARS-CoV-2 was seen experimentally by an
1776 Australian group, Riddell et al [21]. They discovered that SARS-CoV-2 lasts much
1777 longer in the environment away from light than the CoV controls. This is consistent
1778 with the detection of an extraordinarily hard SARS-CoV-2 M by SDMs.

1779
1780 ii) The Dutch group, Ogando et al [79] [69] conducted a viral titration of SARS-CoV-2
1781 that was compared with SARS-CoV-1 and found that the viral titers of SARS-CoV-1
1782 are far higher than those of SARS-CoV-2. This is consistent with the SDM pertaining
1783 to Virulence-Inner shell disorder, which predicts that SARS-CoV-1 will produce more
1784 viral particles in cells and vital organs and, thereby, making the virus more dangerous.

1785
1786 iii) The German group Wolfel et al [29] found that COVID-19 patients shed
1787 much more viral particles than SARS-CoV-1 patients. Again SDMs show the
1788 greatest consistency in explaining this. How do we explain the discrepancy
1789 between (ii) and this discovered mechanism of infectivity? How can we
1790 reconcile greater infectivity with lesser virulence and vice-versa? The “S-
1791 hypothesis” says that SARS-CoV-2 binds to ACE-2 with 10-1000 greater
1792 affinities. If so, how do you account for (ii) and (iii)? SDMs explains that even
1793 though SARS-CoV-2 does not replicate as efficiently as SARS-CoV-1 as a result
1794 of its lower N disorder. It has a much harder M that is more resistant to the
1795 salivary and mucosal anti-microbial enzymes and thus greater amount of viral
1796 sheddings occur.

1797
1798 iv) Why did Hui et al's attempt [78] to show that Omicron (S) binds more
1799 efficiently to upper respiratory tract (ACE-2) instead shows high statistical
1800 correlations with M and N PIDs just as SDMs have predicted [86]?

1801
1802 v) Why is Omicron much milder than previous variants but yet as infectious as
1803 other variants? Once again, SDMs provide an elegant explanation as Omicron
1804 has lower N PIDs and lower or similar M PID when compared to other
1805 variants. The “S-hypothesis” offers an explanation but there are problems with
1806 such an explanation as seen in (iv).

1807
1808 vi) Why was Pang2019 found to be virulent in animal models, viral titrations
1809 and cell plaques, whereas the opposite was found in Pang2017? The S-
1810 hypothesis has no answer especially since all pangolin-CoVs lack FCS. SDMs
1811 have already predicted these even before its discovery.

1812
1813 vii) Why do viral titers of the various SARS-CoV-2 variants, SARS-CoV-2-
1814 related viruses and SARS-CoV-1 correlate with their N PIDs? Why do
1815 attenuation and virulence of the various SARS-CoV-2 variants and SARS-CoV-
1816 1 as determined by animal models and cell plaque studies correlate with N
1817 PID?

1818
1819 viii) What is the nature of long COVID? Again the S-hypothesis has no answer,
1820 whereas SDMs have.

1821
1822 ix) Why are SDMs able to tie the different manifestations of COVID-19 ie
1823 infectivity, virulence and long COVID under an umbrella of three closely
1824 related concepts? The S-hypothesis, on the other hand, still struggles to
1825 understand the role of S in the three manifestations.

1826
1827
1828 There are two factors that determine on how good a model is. These are
1829 reproducibility and reliability. Reproducibility refers to the ability of independent
1830 laboratories getting similar results, whereas reliability involves the ability to
1831 consistently explain and predict the results [146-147]. Therefore, a model that is unable

1832 to be replicated in different independent laboratories is unreproducible, whereas, a
1833 model that is unable to explain a result is unreliable. (i)-(ix) summarizes both the
1834 reproducibility and reliability of SDMs. We would argue that there is definitely
1835 evidence of both as we have seen even though, as we have seen, there are certain
1836 occasions where other proteins such as S, have to be involved in the explanation.

1837
1838 While the experimental work of Riddell et al is crucial in providing evidence that
1839 the abnormally hard M of SARS-CoV-2 is likely to provide greater protection to the
1840 virus, in contrast to other CoVs, there is more that could be done. For instance, there
1841 are a variety of anti-microbial enzymes found in the mucus and saliva but we know
1842 only how they in general can damage viruses. We still don't understand which specific
1843 enzymes can damage or kill viruses SARS-CoV-2 or CoVs [22-28]. Experiments need
1844 to be done on various CoVs with different levels M PIDs and various enzymes [22-28]
1845 so that we can have a better understanding of the mechanisms involved.

1846 1847 7.2. *Links Between Virulence and Infectivity*

1848
1849 An important part of reproducibility and reliability of a model or paradigm is its
1850 ability to explain certain results or certain phenomena. We have seen how SDMs are
1851 not only able to explain virulence and infectivity but also are able to link infectivity and
1852 virulence. The two manifestations are related as virulence involves the ability of the
1853 virus to infect cells in vital organs such the virus is able to overwhelm vital organs
1854 especially the lungs, whereas infectivity pertains to virus' ability to leave the body to
1855 infect the cells of other hosts. We can see that the two manifestations are related but
1856 how are they exactly related is complex. A conundrum is quickly seen: Why is SARS-
1857 CoV-2 less virulent than SARS-CoV-1 but is more infectious? How did the viruses
1858 accomplish this? The S-alone hypothesis is unable to provide a clear answer without
1859 further complications and questions (see (iv) in 7.1 and MCC), whereas the SDMs have
1860 coherent and clearcut answers to this. According to SDMs, when the virus have higher
1861 N disorder (N PID), the virus is able to replicate more quickly because greater disorder
1862 at N provides for more efficient protein-protein/RNA/DNA/lipid binding and therefore
1863 more efficient and rapid replication. If that is the case, then why is SARS-CoV-1 less
1864 infectious than SARS-CoV-2 since MCC entail transportation of much of the viral
1865 particles to the nasal region to be expelled ? Again, SDMs have a novel answer and it
1866 has to do with the much harder outer shell (lower M PID) found in SARS-CoV-2 and
1867 related virus. This abnormally hard M protects the viral particles from the onslaught of
1868 anti-microbial enzymes found in the mucus and saliva even if all SARS-CoV-2 variants
1869 have lower N PIDs i.e. less efficiencies in replication of viral particles. This is
1870 consistent with Wolfel et al's clinical data showing that COVID-19 patients shed much
1871 larger amount of virus. As we can see, a more correct approach comes with a
1872 coordinated understanding of the roles of M, N and S.
1873

1874 7.3. *Pangolin Footprints in the Evolution of COVID-19*

1875
1876 The phrase “pangolin footprints” refers to a set of molecular signatures
1877 that were left behind by the intimate evolutionary interactions COVID-19
1878 ancestral strains had with pangolins. These signatures that involve the
1879 abnormally hard M and the trend towards lower N disorder arose from the
1880 pangolins' burrowing habit, which entails a harder outer and often inner viral
1881 shell to facilitate oral-fecal transmission via buried feces. These features or
1882 pangolin footprints are clinically manifested in the symptoms, infectiousness,
1883 and attenuation/virulence of COVID-19. A review of current knowledge of
1884 immunology indicates that it is also manifested as long COVID. The
1885 abnormally hard M that facilitates greater infectiousness by being resistant to
1886 antimicrobial enzymes in the saliva and mucus could also resist attempts by
1887 the immune system to get rid of it in other ways, thus leading to long COVID.
1888
1889

1890 7.4. *Clues Pointing to Pangolin Footprints in the Evolution of COVID-19*

1891
1892

1893 A unique and highly unusual property that involves all examined SARS-CoV-2-
1894 related viruses is its hard outer shell (low M PID). This property is very rarely found
1895 even among the CoV family. What is the evolutionary origin of this peculiar
1896 characteristic? A retrospective search of our disorder database of CoVs provided us
1897 with a clue when it was found that very few CoVs have such exceptionally hard M and
1898 those found were associated with a burrowing animal such as rabbits. Furthermore, it
1899 can be seen that phylogenetic trees using M have a much closer relationship to SARS-
1900 CoV-2 than previous phylogenetic trees have shown. How can this be even possible
1901 when RaTG13 has 96.4% to SARS-CoV-2, whereas pangolin-CoVs have
1902 approximately only 90% similarity to SARS-CoV-2? What is even more puzzling is
1903 that one of our trees shows that Omicron has a closer relationship to pangolin-CoVs
1904 than to the other variants. The answer has to do with the fact that phylogenetic
1905 algorithms do not handle recombinations well and M may be the best choice for
1906 phylogenetic studies since M is abnormally structured (low disorder), which means that
1907 it is likely to be highly conserved. Secondly, many scientists have been looking for an
1908 intermediary animal host for SARS-CoV-2 to no avail. It has obviously not occurred to
1909 many scientists that there is no intermediary animal host is likely because the ancestral
1910 virus has entered and re-entered the human population and other animal populations
1911 over a long time of time with a primary or secondary reservoir being pangolins. This
1912 could explain how all SARS-CoV-2 related virus have unusually hard M and SARS-
1913 CoV-2 is highly infectious not just to humans but also to a wide range of animals. It
1914 takes time for the virus to become highly adapted to such a wide variety of animals. **All**
1915 **these present clues of a more unique evolutionary relationship between pangolins and**
1916 **SARS-CoV-2 that needs to be further research as there are hints that the resulting**
1917 **characteristics are related to the behaviors and clinical manifestations of the virus.**
1918
1919

1920 7.5. Greater Reproducibility and Reliability When M, N and S are Used in 1921 Coordination

1922
1923
1924
1925 There is thus far no current review article based on updated data
1926 attempting to demonstrate the reproducibility that S is the main protein or sole
1927 protein responsible for the infectivity or pathogenesis, especially when
1928 compared to other viral proteins such as M and N. As we have shown, there is
1929 indisputably important clinical and experimental evidence that shows that S
1930 cannot account for the difference in virulence and infectivity between SARS-
1931 CoV-1 and SARS-CoV-2, even though there is definitely some evidence of its
1932 role in modulating infectivity including antibody evasion via S mutation. The
1933 behaviors of N and M via SDMs can account for much of the clinical and
1934 experimental results and are highly reproducible even to the smallest details.
1935 There are important fundamental biological reasons for this. While S is
1936 important for viral entry and antibody recognition [109], it is not the most
1937 abundant protein. N and M are the most abundant proteins in the infected cell
1938 and virion, respectively [109].

1939 Furthermore, viral entry is only the initial, albeit highly important, step in
1940 the multistep process of the virus life-cycle. We have, however, also seen that
1941 the roles of S in infectivity and virulence become clearer and more consistent
1942 when we examine other proteins, especially M and N, alongside S. The
1943 interplaying roles among the various proteins have to be considered before we
1944 can fully understand the actual nature of these proteins and their impacts on
1945 infectivity and pathogenesis. Without S's greater adaption to ACE-2, there
1946 would be inefficient viral entry, if any, but without the hard M and varying N
1947 disorder there would not be any highly sustainable infectivity or the diverse
1948 levels of virulence respectively seen in COVID-19.

1949 Also, as mentioned, **S alone** cannot account for the differences in
1950 infectivity and virulence between SARS-CoV-1 and SARS-CoV-2 **without**
1951 **further questions**, given current clinical and experimental data. N and M, on
1952 the other hand, do **provide a coherently novel explanation that should be**
1953 **further explored**. It is also worth noting that many laboratories have shown
1954 that it is easy for S to adapt to the ACE-2 even within respiratory cells [133-135],
1955 but it is extremely difficult to find CoVs with such a hard M as in the case of
1956 SARS-CoV-2-related viruses [4,18-20,52-54]. Acquiring such hard M which is
1957 necessary for potential high infectivity had to take its time to evolve from the

interactions with a burrowing animal, i.e. pangolins, and none of the high COVID infectivity we have seen would have been possible with this crucial evolution. Furthermore, it has been argued that nothing is unique about SARS-CoV-2, including its FCS, since it is not difficult to find CoVs with similar properties. In our dataset, we are, however, unable to find CoVs with such an abnormally hard M among CoVs not associated with a burrowing animal, and there are very few CoVs associated with a burrowing animal, if we don't count COVID-19-related viruses.

7.6. Long COVID

Furthermore, S is not able offer a plausible hypothesis for the cause of long COVID. The cause of long COVID has thus far remained a complete mystery, which is a great hindrance for the search for more effective treatments. The M and, to a much smaller extent, N via SDMS, however, offer an elaborate and highly plausible explanation using our current knowledge of immunology on the cause of long COVID: the hard outer shell of the virus is likely to make it difficult for macrophages, T-Cells, and other such entities to get rid of the virus. As a result, there may be plenty of opportunities for the virus to dwell in the macrophages, which are a likely reservoir.

7.7 Clues for Further Research

We have seen that SDMs offers a novel coherent that links virulence and infectivity with N and M via protein intrinsic disorder. Both experimental and computational evidence of the reliability and reproducibility [146-147] of SDMs as applied to COVID-19 is covered. We have tried to show that SDMs using N and M are by and large reproducible when experimental and clinical data especially from other laboratories are scrutinized. The reason for reproducibility and reliability of M and N can arguably be traced to the abundance of the major proteins and their important roles in the replication process. The role of M in infectivity is based on the observation of an abnormally hard SARS-CoV-2 M using AI. Interestingly, phylogenetic study of SARS-CoV-2 related viruses points to a closer relationship between pangolin-CoVs and SARS-CoV-2. This has not been shown in any other phylogenetic study using other proteins or entire genome. While evidence of the reproducibility and reliability of SDMs as applied to COVID-19 using N and M has been presented, further experimental and clinical research is needed to re-affirm their reproducibility and reliability [146-147].

Even though M and N are the most abundant proteins in the virion and cell respectively, there are 29 CoV viral proteins, of which many are also involved in replication and virulence. For this reason, we have tried to show that much of the limitations of COVID-19 SDMs arise from this fact. A solution would be to include more proteins such as S and NSP7 as discussed. This is where further research is also necessary since the current SDMs incorporate only N and M.

While we tried to argue using the existing framework of SDMs and current knowledge of immunology that SDMs as applied to long COVID is promising, the models as currently applied to long COVID are still preliminary or at its infancy and, therefore, rely on circumstantial evidence. Given that long COVID is still largely a mystery, it is imperative that long COVID be further researched into using novel means including SDMs.

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2027 **Author Contributions:** Conceptualization, G.K.-M.G.; data curation, G.K.-M.G. and
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2029 G.K.-M.G.; resources, A.K.D. and J.A.F.; software, G.K.-M.G.; validation, G.K.-M.G.;
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2038 Availability Statements in section “MDPI Research Data Policies” at
2039 <https://www.mdpi.com/ethics>. If the study did not report any data, you might add
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2042 BioComputing, Singapore. He has written a book, “The Viral Shapeshifters: Strange
2043 Behaviors of HIV and Other Viruses” [4]. The authors declare no other conflict of
2044 interest.

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2048 **References**

- 2049
2050
2051
2052 1. WHO. Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic. Available online:
2053 <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019> (accessed on 2 January 2025).
2054
2055 2. CDC Museum COVID-19 Timeline. Available online:
2056 <https://www.cdc.gov/museum/timeline/covid19.html> (accessed on 1 January 2025).
2057
2058 3. Woldometer: COVID-19 Coronavirus Pandemic. Available online:
2059 <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/> (accessed on 2 January 2025).
2060
2061 4. Goh, G.K. *Viral Shapeshifters: Strange Behaviors of HIV and Other Viruses*; Simplicity Research Institute:
2062 Singapore, 2017.
2063
2064 5. Zhang, Z.; Nomura N.; Muramoto Y.; et al. Structure of SARS-CoV-2 Membrane Protein Essential for
2065 Virus Assembly. *Nat. Commun.* **2022**, *13*, 4399. doi:/10.1138/s41467-022-32019-3.
2066
2067 6. Wang Y. ; Xia B.; Gao Z. A Comprehensive Review of Current Insights into the Virulence Factor of SARS-
2068 CoV-2. *J. Vir.* **2025**, *99*,e02049.
2069
2070 7. Miniguloc N.; BoranBayev K.; et. al. Structural Proteins Proteins of Human Coronaviruses: What Makes
2071 Thme Different? *Front. Cell. Infect. Microbial.* **2024**, *14*,1458383. doi: [10.3389/fcimb.2024.1458383](https://doi.org/10.3389/fcimb.2024.1458383).
2072
2073 8. Van Damme E.; Abeywicrema P.; et. al. A Small-Molecule SARS-CoV-2 Inhibitor Targeting the
2074 Membrane Protein. *Nature* **2025**, *640*, 506-513. doi: [10.1038/s41586-025-08651-6](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-08651-6).
2075

- 2076 9. Shang, J.; Ye, G.; Shi, K.; Wan, Y.; Luo, C.; Aihara, H.; Geng, Q.; Auerbach, A.; Li, F. Structural basis of
2077 receptor recognition by SARS-CoV-2. *Nature* **2020**, *581*, 221– 224, DOI: 10.1038/s41586-020-2179-y
2078
- 2079 10. Piplani, S.; Singh, P. K.; Winkler, D. A.; Petrovsky, N. In silico comparison of SARS-CoV-2 spike protein-
2080 ACE2 binding affinities across species and implications for virus origin. *Sci. Rep.* **2021**, *11*, 13063, DOI:
2081 10.1038/s41598-021-92388-5
2082
- 2083 11. Wrapp D.; et. al. Cryo-EM Structure of the 2019-nCoV Spike in the Prefusion Conformation. *Science*
2084 **2020**, *1263*. doi: [10.1126/science.abb2507](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abb2507).
2085
- 2086 12. Keshta A.S.; Mallah S.I.; et. al. COVID-19 VS SARS: A Comparative Review *J. Infect. Public Health.* **2021**,
2087 *14*;967-977 doi: 10.1016/j.jiph.2021.04.007.
2088
- 2089 13. RIDAO: Rapid Intrinsic Disorder Analysis Online. Available online: https://ridao.app/users/sign_in
2090 (accessed on 1 January 2025).
2091
- 2092 14. PONDR[®]: Prediction of Naturally Disordered Regions. Available online: <https://www.pondr.com/>
2093 (accessed on 28 May 2025).
2094
- 2095 15. Garner, E.; Romero, P.; Dunker, A.K.; Brown, C.; Obradovic, Z. Predicting Binding Regions within
2096 Disordered Proteins. *Genome Inform Ser Workshop Genome Inform* **1999**, *10*, 41-50
2097 .
- 2098 16. Cheng, Y.; Oldfield, C.J.; Meng, J.; Romero, P.; Uversky, V.N.; Dunker, A.K. Mining alpha-helix-forming
2099 molecular recognition features with cross species sequence alignments. *Biochemistry* **2007**, *46*, 13468-13477,
2100 doi:10.1021/bi7012273.
2101
- 2102 17. Li, X.; Romero, P.; Rani, M.; Dunker, A.K.; Obradovic, Z. Predicting Protein Disorder
2103 for N-, C-, and Internal Regions. *Genome Inform Ser Workshop Genome Inform* **1999**, *10*, 30-40.
2104
- 2105 18. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. Shell Disorder Analysis Suggests That Pangolins
2106 Offered a Window for a Silent Spread of an Attenuated SARS-CoV-2 Precursor among Humans. *J Proteome*
2107 *Res* **2020**, *19*, 4543-4552, doi:10.1021/acs.jproteome.0c00460.
2108
- 2109 19. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. Rigidity of the Outer Shell Predicted by a Protein
2110 Intrinsic Disorder Model Sheds Light on the COVID-19 (Wuhan-2019-nCoV) Infectivity. *Biomolecules* **2020**,
2111 *10*, doi:10.3390/biom10020331.
2112
- 2113 20. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. Shell disorder analysis predicts greater resilience of
2114 the SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19) outside the body and in body fluids. *Microb Pathog* **2020**, *144*, 104177,
2115 doi:10.1016/j.micpath.2020.104177.
2116
- 2117 21. Riddell S.; Goldie S.; Hill A.; Eagles D.; Drew T. W.; et al. The effect of temperature on persistence of
2118 SARS-CoV-2 on common surfaces. *Virol. J.* **2020**, *17*, 145.10.1186/s12985-020-01418-7.
2119
- 2120 22. Mandel, I.D. The functions of saliva. *J. Dent. Res.* **1987**, *66*, 623–627.
2121
- 2122 23. Ganz, T. Antimicrobial polypeptides in host defense of the respiratory tract. *J. Clin. Investig.* **2002**, *109*,
2123 693–697
2124
- 2125 24. Cole, A.M.; Dewan, P.; Ganz, T. Innate antimicrobial activity of nasal secretions. *Infect Immun* **1999**, *67*,
2126 3267-3275, doi:10.1128/IAI.67.7.3267-3275.1999.
2127 .
- 2128 25. Malamud, D.; Abrams, W.R.; Barber, C.A.; Weissman, D.; Rehtanz, M.; Golub, E. Antiviral activities in
2129 human saliva. *Adv Dent Res* **2011**, *23*, 34-37, doi:10.1177/0022034511399282.
2130

- 2131 26. Chatterjee M. ; Van Putten J.P.M.; Strijbis K. Defensive Properties of Mucin Glycoproteins during
2132 Respiratory Infections-Relevance for SARS-CoV-2. *MBio* **2020**, *11*, e02374-20. doi: 10.1128/mBio.02374-20.
2133
- 2134 27. Bakshari C.R. ; Morales-Gracia A.L.; Althaus M.; et al. Evolutionary Conservation of Antimicrobial
2135 Function of Mucus: A First Defence Against Infection. *NPJ Biofilms Microbiomes* **2018**, *4*, 14. doi:
2136 10.1038/s41522-018-0057-2
2137
- 2138 28. Wilson S.S.; Wiens M.E.; et. al. Defensins at Mucosal Surface: Latest Insights into Defensin-Virus
2139 Interactions. *J. Virol.* **2016**, *90*, 5216-8. doi: 10.1128/JVI.00904-15.
2140
- 2141 29. Wolfel, R.; Corman, V.M.; Guggemos, W.; Seilmaier, M.; Zange, S.; Muller, M.A.; Niemeyer, D.; Jones,
2142 T.C.; Vollmar, P.; Rothe, C., et al. Virological assessment of hospitalized patients with COVID-2019. *Nature*
2143 **2020**, *581*, 465-469, doi:10.1038/s41586-020-2196-x.
2144
- 2145 30. Wright, P.E.; Dyson, H.J. Intrinsically unstructured proteins: re-assessing the protein structure-function
2146 paradigm. *J Mol Biol* **1999**, *293*, 321-331, doi:10.1006/jmbi.1999.3110.
2147
- 2148 31. Barlow R.B.; Dyson H.J.; Wright P.E. Expanding the Paradigm: Intrinsically Disordered Proteins and
2149 Allosteric Regulation *J. Mol. Biol.* **2018**, *430*, 2309-2320, doi: 10.1016/j.jmb.2018.04.003.
2150
- 2151 32. Longhi, S.; Bloyet, L.M.; Gianni, S.; Gerlier, D. How order and disorder within paramyxoviral
2152 nucleoproteins and phosphoproteins orchestrate the molecular interplay of transcription and replication.
2153 *Cell. Mol. Life Sci.* **2017**, *74*, 3091–3118.
2154
- 2155 33. Habchi, J.; Longhi, S. Structural disorder within paramyxovirus nucleoprotein and phosphoproteins.
2156 *Mol. Biosyst.* **2012**, *8*, 69–81
2157
- 2158 34. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Uversky, V.N. Correlating Flavivirus virulence and levels of intrinsic disorder
2159 in shell proteins: protective roles vs. immune evasion. *Mol Biosyst* **2016**, *12*, 1881-1891,
2160 doi:10.1039/c6mb00228e.
2161
- 2162 35. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. Zika and Flavivirus Shell Disorder: Virulence and
2163 Fetal Morbidity. *Biomolecules* **2019**, *9*, doi:10.3390/biom9110710.
2164
- 2165 36. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. Nipah shell disorder, modes of infection, and
2166 virulence. *Microb Pathog* **2020**, *141*, 103976, doi:10.1016/j.micpath.2020.103976.
2167
- 2168 37. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Uversky, V.N. Detection of links between Ebola nucleocapsid and virulence
2169 using disorder analysis. *Mol Biosyst* **2015**, *11*, 2337-2344, doi:10.1039/c5mb00240k.
2170
- 2171 38. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. Feasibility of the vaccine development for SARS-
2172 CoV-2 and other viruses using the shell disorder analysis. *Pac Symp Biocomput* **2021**, *26*, 143-153.
2173
- 2174 39. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. A Novel Strategy for the Development of Vaccines
2175 for SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19) and Other Viruses Using AI and Viral Shell Disorder. *J Proteome Res* **2020**, *19*,
2176 4355-4363, doi:10.1021/acs.jproteome.0c00672.
2177
- 2178 40. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. A Study on the Nature of SARS-CoV-2 Using the
2179 Shell Disorder Models: Reproducibility, Evolution, Spread, and Attenuation. *Biomolecules* **2022**, *12*, 1353.
2180
- 2181 41. Li, X.; Zai, J.; Zhao, Q.; Nie, Q.; Li, Y.; Foley, B.T.; Chaillon, A. Evolutionary history, potential
2182 intermediate animal host, and cross-species analyses of SARS-CoV-2. *J Med Virol* **2020**, *92*, 602-611,
2183 doi:10.1002/jmv.25731.
2184

- 2185 42. Zhou, P.; Yang, X.L.; Wang, X.G.; Hu, B.; Zhang, L.; Zhang, W.; Si, H.R.; Zhu, Y.; Li, B.; Huang, C.L., et
2186 al. Addendum: A pneumonia outbreak associated with a new coronavirus of probable bat origin. *Nature*
2187 **2020**, *588*, E6, doi:10.1038/s41586-020-2951-z.
- 2188
- 2189 43. Hu, B.; Guo, H.; Zhou, P.; Shi, Z.L. Characteristics of SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19. *Nat Rev Microbiol* **2021**,
2190 *19*, 141-154, doi:10.1038/s41579-020-00459-7.
- 2191
- 2192 44. Lam, T.T.; Jia, N.; Zhang, Y.W.; Shum, M.H.; Jiang, J.F.; Zhu, H.C.; Tong, Y.G.; Shi, Y.X.; Ni, X.B.; Liao,
2193 Y.S., et al. Identifying SARS-CoV-2-related coronaviruses in Malayan pangolins. *Nature* **2020**, *583*, 282-285,
2194 doi:10.1038/s41586-020-2169-0.
- 2195
- 2196 45. Xiao, K.; Zhai, J.; Feng, Y.; Zhou, N.; Zhang, X.; Zou, J.J.; Li, N.; Guo, Y.; Li, X.; Shen, X., et al. Isolation
2197 of SARS-CoV-2-related coronavirus from Malayan pangolins. *Nature* **2020**, *583*, 286-289, doi:10.1038/s41586-
2198 020-2313-x.
- 2199
- 2200 46. Fan, H.-H.; Wang, L.-Q.; Liu, W.-L.; An, X.-P.; Liu, Z.-D.; He, X.-Q.; Song, L.-H.; Tong, Y.-G.
2201 Repurposing of clinically approved drugs for treatment of coronavirus disease 2019 in a 2019-novel
2202 coronavirus-related coronavirus model. *Chinese medical journal* **2020**, *133*, 1051-1056.
- 2203
- 2204 47. Zhang, T.; Wu, Q.; Zhang, Z. Probable Pangolin Origin of SARS-CoV-2 Associated with the COVID-19
2205 Outbreak. *Curr Biol* **2020**, *30*, 1346-1351 e1342, doi:10.1016/j.cub.2020.03.022.
- 2206
- 2207 48. Liu P.; Jiang J.Z.; et. al. Are Pangolins the Intermediate Host of the the 2019 Novel Coronavirus (SARS-
2208 CoV-2)? *PLoS Pathogl.* **2021**, *16*, e1009664. doi: 10.1371/journal.ppat.1009664. .
- 2209
- 2210 49. Nga NTT, Latinne A, Thuy HB, Long NV, Ngoc PTB, et al. Evidence of SARS-CoV-2 Related
2211 Coronaviruses Circulating in Sunda pangolins (*Manis javanica*) Confiscated From the Illegal Wildlife Trade in
2212 Viet Nam. *Front Public Health* **2022**, *10*, 826116. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2022.826116.
- 2213
- 2214 50. Temmam S, Vongphayloth K, Baquero E, Munier S, Bonomi M, et al. Bat coronaviruses related to SARS-
2215 CoV-2 and infectious for human cells. *Nature* **2022**, *604*. 330-336. doi: 10.1038/s41586-022-04532-4.
- 2216
- 2217 51. 47. Temmam S.; Montegutelli X.; Herate C.; et al. SARS-CoV-2 Related Bat Virus Behavior in Human-
2218 relevant Models Sheds Light on the Origin of COVID-19. *EMBO*
2219 **2023**, *5*;:e56055. doi: 10.15252/embr.202256055.
- 2220 .
- 2221 52. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. Computational, Experimental, and Clinical
2222 Evidence of a Specific but Peculiar Evolutionary Nature of (COVID-19) SARS-CoV-2. *J Proteome Res* **2022**,
2223 *10.1021/acs.jproteome.2c00001*, doi:10.1021/acs.jproteome.2c00001.
- 2224
- 2225 53. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Uversky, V.N. Understanding Viral Transmission Behavior via Protein
2226 Intrinsic Disorder Prediction: Coronaviruses. *J Pathog* **2012**, *2012*, 738590, doi:10.1155/2012/738590.
- 2227
- 2228 54. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Uversky, V. Prediction of Intrinsic Disorder in MERS-CoV/HCoV-EMC
2229 Supports a High Oral-Fecal Transmission. *PLoS Curr* **2013**, *5*,
2230 doi:10.1371/currents.outbreaks.22254b58675cdebc256dbe3c5aa6498b.
- 2231
- 2232 55. Wei, L.; Song, L.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N.; Goh, G.K.-M. A Comparative Experimental
2233 and Computational Study on the Nature of the Pangolin-CoV and COVID-19 Omicron. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **2024**,
2234 *25*, 753
- 2235
- 2236 56. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. Shell Disorder Models Detect That Omicron Has
2237 Harder Shells with Attenuation but Is Not a Descendant of the Wuhan-Hu-1 SARS-CoV-2. *Biomolecules* **2022**,
2238 *12*, 631.

2239
2240 57. Gheorghita R.; Soldanescu I.; Lobiuc A.; et. al. The Knowns and Unknowns of long COVID form
2241 Mechanisms to Therapeutical. *Front. Immunol.* **2024**, *15*, 1344086. doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2024.1344086.
2242
2243 58. Lai C. C.; Hsu C. K.; Yen M. Y.; et al. Long COVID: An Inevitable Sequela of SARS-CoV-2 Infection. *J J.*
2244 *Microbiol. Immunolo. Infect.* **2023**, *56*,1-9. doi: 10.1016/j.jmii.2022.10.003.
2245
2246 59. Post COVID-19 Condition (Long COVID). Available Online: [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/post-covid-19-condition-(long-covid))
2247 [sheets/detail/post-covid-19-condition-\(long-covid\).](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/post-covid-19-condition-(long-covid))(accessed on 28 September 2025).
2248
2249 60. Are Long COVID Sufferers Falling Through the Cracks?. Available Online::
2250 <https://med.stanford.edu/news/insights/2024/03/long-covid-symptoms-sufferers-misdiagnosed.html>
2251 (accessed on 28 September 2025).
2252
2253 61. Erlandson K.M.; Geng L.N.; et. al. Differentiation of Prior SARS-CoV-2 Infection and postacute Sequelae
2254 by Standard Clinical Laboratory Measurements in RECOVER Cohort. *Ann. Intern. Med.* **2024**, *177*, 1209-1221.
2255 doi:10.7326/M24-0737.
2256
2257 62. Marshall M.; The Four Most Urgent Questions About Long COVID. *Nature* **2021**, *594*,168-170. doi: /
2258 10.1038/d41586-021-01511-z
2259
2260 63. Levin J.; Bradshaw M. The Challenge of Long COVID: Is the Pandemic Really Over? *Public Health Rep.*
2261 **2025**, 333549251358665. doi: 10.1177/00333549251358665. 177, 1209-1221. doi:10.7326/M24-0737.
2262
2263 64. Patcai J.; Is “Long COVID” Similar to “Long SARS”? *Oxford Open Immunology* **2022**, *3*,iqac002. doi: /
2264 [10.1093/oxfimm/iqac002](https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfimm/iqac002)
2265
2266 65. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Uversky, V.N. Protein intrinsic disorder toolbox for comparative analysis of
2267 viral proteins. *BMC Genomics* **2008**, *9 Suppl 2*, S4, doi:10.1186/1471-2164-9-S2-S4.
2268
2269 66. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Uversky, V.N. A comparative analysis of viral matrix proteins using disorder
2270 predictors. *Virol J* **2008**, *5*, 126, doi:10.1186/1743-422X-5-126.
2271
2272 67. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. HIV Vaccine Mystery and Viral Shell Disorder.
2273 *Biomolecules* **2019**, *9*, doi:10.3390/biom9050178.
2274
2275 68. Tompa, P. Intrinsically unstructured proteins. *Trends Biochem Sci* **2002**, *27*, 527-533, doi:10.1016/s0968-
2276 0004(02)02169-2.
2277
2278 69. UniProt. Available online: <https://www.uniprot.org/> (accessed on 22 January 2025).
2279
2280 70. NCBI-Protein/Genbank. Available online: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/protein> (accessed on 22
2281 March 2022).
2282
2283 71. European_CDC. European Center for Disease Prevention and Control, Weekly epidemiological update:
2284 Omicron variant of concern (VOC). Available online: [https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/news-](https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/news-events/weekly-epidemiological-update-omicron-variant-concern-voc-week-2-data-20-january-2022)
2285 [events/weekly-epidemiological-update-omicron-variant-concern-voc-week-2-data-20-january-2022](https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/news-events/weekly-epidemiological-update-omicron-variant-concern-voc-week-2-data-20-january-2022)
2286 (accessed on 28 January 2025).
2287
2288 72. Wolter, N.; Jassat, W.; Walaza, S.; Welch, R.; Moultrie, H.; Groome, M.; Amoako, D.G.; Everatt, J.;
2289 Bhiman, J.N.; Scheepers, C. Early assessment of the clinical severity of the SARS-CoV-2 Omicron variant in
2290 South Africa: A data linkage study. *Lancet* **2022**, .399.437-446,doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(22)00017-4
2291

- 2292 73. Abdullah, F.; Myers, J.; Basu, D.; Tintinger, G.; Ueckermann, V.; Mathebula, M.; Ramlall, R.; Spoor, S.;
2293 de Villiers, T.; Van der Walt, Z., et al. Decreased severity of disease during the first global omicron variant
2294 covid-19 outbreak in a large hospital in tshwane, south africa. *Int J Infect Dis* **2022**, *116*, 38-42,
2295 doi:10.1016/j.ijid.2021.12.357.
- 2296
- 2297 74. Lu, S.; Luo, S.; Liu, C.; Li, M.; et al. Induction of significant neutralizing antibodies against SARS-CoV-2
2298 by a highly attenuated pangolin coronavirus variant with a 104nt deletion at the 3'-UTR. *Emerg. Microbes*
2299 *Infect.* **2023**, *12*, 2151383.
- 2300
- 2301 75. Guo Z.; Zhang C.; Zhang C.; Cui H. et al. SARS-CoV-2-related pangolin coronavirus exhibits similar
2302 infection characteristics to SARS-CoV-2 and direct contact transmissibility in hamsters. *Science* **2022**, *25*,
2303 104350. doi: 10.1016/j.isci.2022.104350.
- 2304
- 2305 76. Liu M.Q.; Lin H.F.; et. al. A SARS-CoV-2-Related Virus from Malayan Pangolins Causes Lung Infection
2306 without Severe Diseases in Human ACE2-Transgenic Mice. *J. Virol.* **2023**, *97*;e01971922. doi:
2307 10.1128/jvi.01719-22.
- 2308
- 2309 77. Shuai H.; Chan J.F.W; et. al. Attenuated Replication and Pathogenicity of SARS-CoV-2 B.1.1 Omicron .
2310 *Nature* **2022**, *603*,693-699. doi: [10.1038/s41586-022-04442-5](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-04442-5)
- 2311
- 2312 78. Hui K.P.Y.; Ho J.C.W.; Cheung M.C.; et al. SARS-CoV-2 Omicron variant replication in human
2313 bronchus and lung ex vivo. *Nature* **2022**, *603*,715-720. doi: 10.1038/s41586-022-04479-6. Epub 2022 Feb 1.
2314 PMID: 35104836.
- 2315
- 2316 79. Ogando, N.S.; Dalebout, T.J.; Zevenhoven-Dobbe, J.C.; Limpens, R.; van der Meer, Y.; Caly, L.; Druce, J.;
2317 de Vries, J.J.C.; Kikkert, M.; Barcena, M., et al. SARS-coronavirus-2 replication in Vero E6 cells: replication
2318 kinetics, rapid adaptation and cytopathology. *J Gen Virol* **2020**, *101*, 925-940, doi:10.1099/jgv.0.001453.
- 2319
- 2320 80. Liang X.; Chen X.; et. al. Pathogenicity, Tissue Tropism and Potential Vertical Transmission of SARS-
2321 CoV-2 in Malayan Pangolins. *PLoS. Pathog.* **2023**, *19*, e10111384 doi: [10.1388/s41392-023-01449-w](https://doi.org/10.1388/s41392-023-01449-w).
- 2322
- 2323 81. Hou, Y.J.; Chiba, S.; Leist, S.R.; Meganck, R.M.; Martinez, D.R.; Schafer, A.; Catanzaro, N.J.; Sontake, V.;
2324 West, A.; Edwards, C.E.; et al. Host range, transmissibility and antigenicity of a pangolin coronavirus. *Nat.*
2325 *Microbiol.* **2023**, *8*, 1820–1833.
- 2326
- 2327 82. Huang X.Y.; Chen Q.; et. al. A Pangolin-Origin SARS-CoV-2-Related Coronavirus: Infectivity,
2328 Pathogenicity, and Cross-Protection by Preexisting Immunity Cell *Discov.* **2023**, *9*;:59. doi: 10.1038/s41421-
2329 023-00557-9.
- 2330
- 2331 83. Mire, C. E.; Satterfield, B. A.; Geisbert, J. B.; Agans, K. N.; Borisevich, V.; Yan, L.; Chan, Y.-P.; Cross, R.
2332 W.; Fenton, K. A.; Broder, C. C.; Geisbert, T. W. Pathogenic differences between Nipah virus Bangladesh and
2333 Malaysia strains in primates: Implications for antibody therapy. *Sci. Rep.* **2016**, *6*, 30916, DOI:
2334 10.1038/srep30916
- 2335
- 2336 84. CDC: Avian Influenza (Bird Flu). Available online: [https://www.cdc.gov/bird-flu/virus-](https://www.cdc.gov/bird-flu/virus-transmission/index.html)
2337 [transmission/index.html](https://www.cdc.gov/bird-flu/virus-transmission/index.html) (accessed on 28 May 2025).
- 2338
- 2339 85. Yehia N.; Salem H.M.; et. al. Common Viral and Bacterial Respiratory Infections: An Updated Review.
2340 *Poult. Sci.* **2023**, *102*;:102553. doi: 10.1016/j.psj.2023.102553. Epub 2023 Feb 1. PMID: 36965253; PMCID:
2341 PMC10064437.
- 2342
- 2343 86. Psittacosis Pneumonia .Available online: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK526005/> (Last
2344 Accessed: 28 May 2025).
- 2345

- 2346 87. Nguyen X.D.; Zhao Y.; et. al. Modeling Long-Distance Airborne Transmission of Highly Pathogenic
2347 Avian Influenza Carried by Dust Particles. *Sci. Rep.* **2023**, *13*, 16255. doi: [10.1038/s41598-023-42897-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-42897-2).
2348
- 2349 88. Weupe M., Peabody Lever J.E., Kennemur J.P., Bono T.R., Phillips S.E., Shei R.-J., Rowe S.M. Moving
2350 mucus matters for lung health. *Front. Young Minds.* 2019;7:16. doi: 10.3389/frym.2019.00106.
2351
- 2352 89. Fahy, J.B.; Dickey, B.F. Airways mucus function and dysfunction. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2010**, *363*, 2233–2247.
2353
- 2354 90. Abrahams, P. (Ed.) *How the Body Works: A Comprehensive Illustrated Encyclopedia of Anatomy*; Amber
2355 Books Limited: London, UK, 2016.
2356
- 2357 91. Ward HE, Nicholas TE. Alveolar type I and type II cells. *Aust N Z J Med.* 1984 Oct;14(5 Suppl 3):731-4. .
2358
- 2359 92. Gehr, P., Geiser M., Im Hof V. *et al.* Surfactant and Inhaled Particles in the Conducting Airways:
2360 Structural, Stereological, and Biophysical Aspects. *Microsc. Res. Tech.* **1993**, *26*, 324-36.
2361 doi:/10.1002/jemt.1070260510.
2362
- 2363 93. Posada, D. How does recombination affect phylogeny estimation? *Trends Ecol Evol* **2000**, *15*, 489-490,
2364 doi:10.1016/s0169-5347(00)02027-9.
2365
- 2366 94. Kupferschmidt, K. Where did 'weird' Omicron come from? *Science* **2021**, *374*, 1179,
2367 doi:10.1126/science.acx9738.
2368
- 2369 95. Choi, B.; Choudhary, M.C.; Regan, J.; Sparks, J.A.; Padera, R.F.; Qiu, X.; Solomon, I.H.; Kuo, H.H.;
2370 Boucau, J.; Bowman, K., et al. Persistence and Evolution of SARS-CoV-2 in an Immunocompromised Host. *N*
2371 *Engl J Med* **2020**, *383*, 2291-2293, doi:10.1056/NEJMc2031364.
2372
- 2373 96. Wei C., Shan K.J., Wang W., Zhang S., Huan Q., Qian W. Evidence for a mouse origin of the SARS-CoV-
2374 2 Omicron variant. *J. Genet. Genom.* 2021,48,1111–1121. doi: 10.1016/j.jgg.2021.12.003.
2375
- 2376 97. Schmid-Holmes S., Drickamer L.C., Robinson A.S., Gillie L.L. Burrows and burrow-cleaning behavior
2377 of house mice (*Mus musculus domesticus*) *Am. Midl. Nat.* **2001**,*146*,53–62. doi: 10.1674/0003-
2378 0031(2001)146[0053:BABCBO]2.0.CO;2.
2379
- 2380 98. EMBI-EBI: Clustal Omega. Available online: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/Tools/msa/clustalo/> (accessed
2381 on 2 January 2025).
2382
- 2383 99. Sievers F.; Higgins D. G. Clustal Omega for Making Accurate Alignments of Many Protein Sequences.
2384 *Protein Sci.* **2018**. *27*, 135-145. doi: 10.1002/pro.3290.
2385
- 2386 100. TREX: CLUSTALW. Available online: [http://www.trex.uqam.ca/index.php?](http://www.trex.uqam.ca/index.php?action=align&project=trex)
2387 [action=align&project=trex](http://www.trex.uqam.ca/index.php?action=align&project=trex) (accessed on 28 May 2025).
2388
- 2389 101. Garry R. F. SARS-CoV Furin Cleavage Site is not Engineered. *Proc. Nat Acad Sci.* **2022**,
2390 *119*;e2211107119. doi: 10.1073/pnas.2211107119.
2391
- 2392 102. Chan Y. A.; Zhan S. H. The Emergence of the Spike Furin Cleavage Site in SARS-CoV-2 *Mol. Biol. Evol.*
2393 **2022**. *39*, msab327. doi: 10.1093/molbev/msab327.
2394
- 2395 103. Harrison N. L.; Sach J. A Call for an Independent Inquiry into the Origin of the SARS-CoV-2 virus.
2396 *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.* **2022**, *119*;e2202769119. doi: 10.1073/pnas.2202769119.
2397

- 2398 104. Mushebenge, A.G.-A.; Ugbaja, S.C.; Mbatha, N.A.; Khan, R.B.; Kumalo, H.M. A Comprehensive
2399 Analysis of Structural and Functional Changes Induced by SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein Mutations. *COVID*
2400 **2023**, *3*, 1454-1472. <https://doi.org/10.3390/covid3090100>
2401
- 2402 105. Morris R.; Black K. A.; Stollar E. J. Uncovering Protein Functions: From Classification to Complexes.
2403 *Essays Biochem.* **2022**, *66*,255-285. doi: 10.1042/EBC20200108.
2404
- 2405 106. McBride, R.; Van Zyl, M.; Fielding, B.C. The Coronavirus Nucleocapsid Is a Multifunctional Protein.
2406 *Viruses* **2014**, *6*, 2991-3018.
2407
- 2408 107. Bai Z.; Cao Y.; Liu W.; Li J. The SARS-CoV-2 Nucleocapsid Protein and Its Role in Viral Structure,
2409 Biological Functions, and a Potential Target for Drug or Vaccine Migration. *Viruses* **2021**, *13*,1115. doi:
2410 10.3390/v13061115.
2411
- 2412 108. V'kovski P.; Kratzel A.; Steiner S.; et al. Coronavirus Biology and Replication: Implications for SARS-
2413 CoV-2. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **2021**, *19*,:155-170.
2414
- 2415 109. Acheson, N.H. *Fundamentals of Molecular Virology*; Wiley: Hoboken, NJ, USA, 2007
2416
- 2417 110. Machkovec H. M.; Hahn A. M.; et. al. Persistent SARS-CoV-2 Infection,: Significance and Implications.
2418 *Lancet Infect. Dis.* **2024**, *24*,:e453-e462. doi: 10.1016/S1473-3099(23)00815-0.
2419
- 2420 111. Zuo W.; He D.; Liang C.; et al. The Persistence of SARS-CoV-2 in Tissues and its Association with long
2421 COVID Symptoms: A Cross-Sectional Cohort Study in China. *Lancet Infect. Dis.* **2024**, *9*,845-855 doi:
2422 10.1016/S1473-3099(24)00171-3.
2423
- 2424 112. Raigor D. D.; Lee M. H.; et. al. The Many Estimats of the COVID-19 Case Fatality Rate *Lancet Infect.*
2425 *Dis.* **2020**, *20*, 776-777. doi: 10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30244-9.
2426
- 2427 113, Peacock T. P.; Coldhill, D. H.; Zhou J.; et. al. The Furin Cleavage Site is in the SARS-CoV-2 Spike
2428 Protein is Required For Transmission in Ferrets. *Nat. Microbiol.* **2021**, *6*, 899-909, doi:10.1038/s41564-021-
2429 00908-w.
2430
- 2431 114. Su W.; Choy K. T.; Gu H.; et. al. Reduced Pathogenicity and Transmission Potential of Omicron BA.1
2432 and BA.2 Compared with the Early Severe Acute Restpiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 D614G Variant in
2433 Syrian Hamster. *J. Infect. Dis.* **2023**, *227*, e2211107119. doi: 10.1073/pnas.2211107119.
2434
- 2435 115. Yuan S.; Ye Z. W.; et. al. Pathogenicity Transmissibility, and Fitness of SARS-CoV-2 Omicron in Syrian
2436 Hamster. *Science* **2022**, *377*,428-433. doi: 10.1126/science.abn8939.
2437
- 2438 116. Zhang Y. N.; Zhang H. Q.; Li N.; et al. Different Pathogenesis of SARS-CoV-2 Omicron Variant in
2439 Wild-Type Laboratory Mice and Hamster .*Signal Transduct.*
2440 . **2022**, *7*,:62 .doi: 10.1038/s41392-022-00930-2..
2441
- 2442 117. Armando F.; Beythien G.; Kaiser F. K. A. :et. al. SARS-CoV-2 Omicron Variant Causes Mild Pathology
2443 in the Upper and Lower Respiratory Tract of Hamsters. *Nat. Commun.* **2022**, *13*,3519. doi:10.1038/s41467-022-
2444 31200-y
2445
- 2446 118. Tang H.; Shao Y.; et. al. Evolutionary Characteristics of SARS-CoV-2 Omicron Subvariants Adapted to
2447 the Host. *Sig. Transduct. Target Ther.* **2023**, *8*, 211. doi: [10.138/s41392-023-01449-w](https://doi.org/10.138/s41392-023-01449-w).
2448
- 2449 119. R: Statistical Package. Available online: <https://www.r-project.org/> (accessed on 28 May 2025).
2450

- 2451 120. R Core Team. A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing; R Foundation for Statistical
2452 Computing: Vienna, Austria, 2013/
2453
- 2454 121. Castillo G.; Nelli R.K.; et. al. SARS-CoV-2 is More Efficient than HCoV-NL63 in Infecting a Small
2455 Subpopulatiion of ACE2+ Human Respiratory Epithelial Cells. *Viruses* **2023**, *15*:736. doi:
2456 10.3390/v15030736..
2457
- 2458 122. Castillo G.; Mora-Diaz J.C.; et. al. Molecular Mechanism of Human Coronavirus Infection and
2459 Replication. *Virus Res.* **2023**, *327*:199078. doi: 10.1016/j.virusres.2023.199078.
2460
- 2461 123. Lin H. X.; Feng Y.; et. al. Characterization of the Spike Protein of Human Coronavirus NL63 in
2462 Receptor Binding and Pseudotype Virus Entry. *Virus Res.* **2011**, *160*, 283-93. doi:
2463 10.1016/j.virusres.2011.06.029.
2464
- 2465 124. Hofmann H.; van der Hoek L.; et. al. Human Coronavirus NL63 employs the severe acute respiratory
2466 syndrome coronavirus for cellular entry. *PNAS.* **2005**, *102*,7988-93. doi: 10.1073/pnas.0409465102.
2467
- 2468 125. Wang Y.; Li N.; et al. Discovery of a Subgenotype of Human Coronavirus NL63 Associated with
2469 Lower Respiratory Tract Infection in China. *Emerging Microbe Infections* **2018**, *9*, 246-255. doi:
2470 10.1080/10.1080/22221751.2020.171999.
2471
- 2472 126. Abdul-Rasool S. ; Fielding C.: Understanding Human Coronavirus HCoV-NL63. *Open Virol. J.* **2023**,
2473 *4*:76-84. doi: 10.2174/1874357901004010076.
2474
- 2475 127. Calder L.J.; Calcraft T.; et. al. Electron Crytomography of SARS-CoV-2 Virions Reveals Clylinder-
2476 Shaped Particles with a Double Layer RNA Assembly. *Commun. Biol.* **2022**, *5*:1210. doi: [10.1038/s42003-022-
2477 04183-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-022-04183-1).
2478
- 2479 128. Escors D. ; Ortega J.; Laude H.; Ehjuanes L.; The Membrane M Protein Carboxy Terminus Binds to
2480 Transmissible Gastroenteritis. *J. Virol.* **2021**, *75*,1312-24. doi: 10.1128/JVI.75.3.1312-1324.2001.
2481
- 2482 129. Cong Y.; Ulasli M.; et. al. Nucleocapsid Protein Recruitment to Replication-Transcription Complex. *J.*
2483 *Virol.* **2020**, *94*:e01925-19. doi: 10.1128/JVI.01925-19. PMID: 31776274; PMCID: PMC6997762.
2484
2485
- 2486 130. Verheije M.H.; Hagemeyer M.C.; et. al. The Coronavirus Nucleocapsid Protein is Dynamically
2487 Associated with the Replication-Transcription Complexes. *J. Virol.* **2010**, *84*:11575-9. doi: 10.1128/JVI.00569-
2488 10. Epub 2010 Aug 25. PMID: 20739524; PMCID: PMC2953146.
2489
- 2490 131. Lubinski B.; Jaimes J. A.; Whitaker G. R. Intrinsic Furin-mediated Cleavability of the Spike S1/S2 Site
2491 from SARS-CoV-2 Variant B.1.529 (Omicron). *BioRxiv.* **2022**, *26*,2022.04.20.488969. doi:
2492 10.1101/2022.04.20.488969.
2493
- 2494 132. Brown, V. J. Pharmaceuticals : New Insignhs into Thalidomide. *Environ. Health Perspect.* **2009**, *117*, A61.
2495
- 2496 133. Gu H.; Chen Q.; Yang C.; et al. Adaptation of SARS-CoV-2 in BALB/cMice for Testing Vaccine Efficacy
2497 *Science* **2020**, *369*:1603-1607.
2498
- 2499 134. Huang K.; Zhang Y.; et. al. Q493K and Q498H Substitutionx in Spike Promote Adaptation of SARS-
2500 CoV-2 in Mice. *EBioMedicine* **2021**, *67*:103381..
2501
- 2502 135. Montagutelli X.; Prot M.; et. al. A Mouse-Adapted SARS-CoV-2 Strain in Mice. *bioRxiv* **2021**,
2503 <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.07.10.451880>
2504

- 2505 136. West, E. F.; Dkemper C. Complsome – The Intracellular Complement System. *Nat. Rev. Nuephrol.* **2023**,
2506 19, 426-439. doi:10.1038/s41581-023-00704-1
- 2507
- 2508 137. Van Domselaar R.; Bovenchen N. Cell Death-Independent Functions of Granzymes: Hit Viruses Where
2509 It Hurts. *Rev. Med. Virol.* **2011**, 9,302-14 doi: 10.1002/rmv.697.
- 2510
- 2511 138. Trivedi P. C.; Barlett J. J.; Puliniklunil T. L. Lysosomal Biology and Function: Modern View of Cellular
2512 Debris Bin. *Cells* **2023**, 9,113. doi: 10.3390/cells9051131.
- 2513
- 2514 139. Sompayrac, L. *How the Immune Sustum Works 5 Edition*; Wiley Blackwell: Sussex, U.K., 2016.
- 2515
- 2516 140. Gilbert A. S.; Wheeler R. T.; May R. C.. Fungal Pathogens: Survival and Replication within
2517 Macrophages. *Cold Spring Harb. Perspect. Med.*. **2014**, 5,a019661. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2017.01117.
- 2518
- 2519 141. Gavin C.; Menke S.; Heldringl N.; Heck K. A.; et. al. The Complement System is Essential for
2520 Phagocytosis of Mesenchvmak Stomal Cells by Monocytes. *Front. Immunol.* **2019**, 10,2249.doi:
2521 10.3389/fimmu.2019.02249.
- 2522
- 2523 142. Sharma C. ; Bayry J. High Risk of Autoimmune Disease After COVID-19. *Nat. Rev. Rheumatol.*. **2023**,
2524 19,399-400. doi: 10.1038/s41584-023-00964-y.
- 2525
- 2526 143. Ruf W. ; Immune Damage in Long COVID. *Science* **2024**, 383,262-263. doi: 10.1126/science.adn1077.
- 2527
- 2528 144. Huot N.; Planchais C.; et. al. SARS-CoV-2 Viral Persistence in Lung Alveolar Macrophages is
2529 Controlled by IFN- γ and NK cells. *Immunol.* **2023**, 24,;2068-2079. doi: [10.1038/s41590-023-01661-4](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41590-023-01661-4).
- 2530
- 2531 145. Thierry J. ; Liberman J. Perforin: A Key Pore-Forming Protein for Immune Control of Viruses and
2532 Cancer. *Subcell. Biochem.* **2014**, 80,197-220 e2202769119. doi: 10.1007/978-94-017-8881-6_10.
- 2533
- 2534 146. Conceptualizing, Measuring, and Studying Reproducibility. Available Online::
2535 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK350355/> (accessed on 28 May 2025).
- 2536
- 2537 147. Gundersen O. E. The Fundamental Principles of Reproducibility. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A.* **2021**,
2538 379,20200210. doi: [10.1098/rsta.2020.0210](https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2020.0210)
- 2539